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Predictive Collision Avoidance (PCA):
A Novel Pedestrian-Collision Detection System
for Public-Area Mobile Robots
Using Trajectory Forecasting

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ACTA DE L'EXAMEN DEL TREBALL FI DE CARRERA

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va exposar el seu Treball de Fi de Carrera, el qual va tractar sobre el tema següent:

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“It’s a miracle that curiosity survives formal education.”

Albert Einstein

Abstract

The rapid advancement of autonomous navigation systems, such as autonomous vehicles (AVs) and public mobile robots (PMRs), presents significant challenges in ensuring safe, efficient, and socially compliant navigation. In dynamic, human-populated environments, the ability to predict and adapt to the future motion of surrounding pedestrians is crucial. This project integrates state-of-the-art models for human detection, tracking, and trajectory prediction into the navigation stack of a PMR. The primary contribution is the development of the PCA, a novel pedestrian-collision detection module that leverages trajectory forecasting to enable safer and more efficient navigation. To evaluate the system, a custom simulation task was designed, comprising various use cases in both single-agent and multi-agent scenarios. Navigation performance was assessed using the ACAT (Available Collision Avoidance Time) metric, which increased by 87.57 % compared to the baseline configuration, demonstrating statistically significant improvements (p -value < 0.001). These results highlight the potential of the proposed system for integration into the navigation stack of PMRs, offering a robust enhancement for real-time navigation in complex, shared urban environments.

Resumen

El rápido avance de los sistemas de navegación autónomos, como los vehículos autónomos (AV) y los robots móviles públicos (PMR), plantea importantes retos a la hora de garantizar una navegación segura, eficiente y socialmente compatible. En entornos dinámicos y poblados por humanos, es fundamental la capacidad de predecir y adaptarse al movimiento futuro de los peatones que se encuentran en los alrededores. Este proyecto integra modelos de última generación para la detección, el seguimiento y la predicción de la trayectoria de las personas en la pila de navegación de un PMR. La principal contribución es el desarrollo del PCA, un novedoso módulo de detección de colisiones de peatones que aprovecha la predicción de trayectorias para permitir una navegación más segura y eficiente. Para evaluar el sistema, se diseñó una tarea de simulación personalizada, que comprendía varios casos de uso en escenarios tanto de un solo agente como de múltiples agentes. El rendimiento de la navegación se evaluó utilizando la métrica ACAT (Available Collision Avoidance Time), que aumentó en un 87,57 % en comparación con la configuración de referencia, lo que demuestra mejoras estadísticamente significativas (p -valor < 0.001). Estos resultados ponen de relieve el potencial del sistema propuesto para su integración en la pila de navegación de los PMR, lo que supone una mejora considerable para la navegación en tiempo real en entornos urbanos complejos y compartidos.

Resum

El ràpid avenç dels sistemes de navegació autònoms, com ara els vehicles autònoms (AV) i els robots mòbils públics (PMR), presenta reptes importants per garantir una navegació segura, eficient i socialment compatible. En entorns dinàmics i poblats per humans, la capacitat de predir i adaptar-se al moviment futur dels vianants circumdants és crucial. Aquest projecte integra models d'última generació per a la detecció, el seguiment i la predicció de trajectòries humanes a la pila de navegació d'un PMR. La contribució principal és el desenvolupament del PCA, un innovador mòdul de detecció de col·lisions de vianants que aprofita la previsió de trajectòries per permetre una navegació més segura i eficient. Per avaluar el sistema, es va dissenyar una tasca de simulació personalitzada, que comprenia diversos casos d'ús tant en escenaris d'un sol agent com de diversos agents. El rendiment de la navegació es va avaluar mitjançant la mètrica ACAT (Available Collision Avoidance Time), que va augmentar un 87,57 % en comparació amb la configuració de referència, demostrant millores estadísticament significatives (p -valor $< 0,001$). Aquests resultats destaquen el potencial del sistema proposat per a la integració en la pila de navegació dels PMR, oferint una millora robusta per a la navegació en temps real en entorns urbans complexos i compartits.

Keywords

public-area mobile robots, public mobile robots, autonomous urban robots, trajectory prediction, collision detection, collision avoidance, path planning, TIAGo robot.

Palabras clave

robots móviles de área pública, robots móviles públicos, robots urbanos autónomos, predicción de trayectoria, detección de colisiones, evitación de colisiones, planificación de trayectorias, robot TIAGo.

Paraules clau

robots mòbils d'àrea pública, robots mòbils públics, robots urbans autònoms, predicció de trajectòria, detecció de col·lisions, evitació de col·lisions, planificació de trajectòries, robot TIAGo.

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Contents

Declaration of Authorship	iii
Abstract	vii
Resumen	viii
Resum	ix
Agraïments	xi
1 Introduction	1
1.1 Context and Motivation	1
1.2 Problem Statement and Research Gap	2
1.3 Project Aim	2
1.4 Objectives	2
1.4.1 Objective 1	3
1.4.2 Objective 2	3
1.4.3 Objective 3	3
1.4.4 Objective 4	3
1.4.5 Objective 5	3
1.4.6 Objective 6	4
2 Related Work	5
2.1 Introduction to PMRs	5
2.2 Key technologies in PMRs	6
2.2.1 Perception	6
Sensors	6
Sensor noise and its impact on accuracy	9
Sensor fusion	9
2.2.2 Localization	10
2.2.3 Mapping	11
2.2.4 Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (SLAM)	12
2.2.5 Path Planning	13
Global planning	14
Local planning	15
2.3 Simulation Tools for PMRs	16
2.4 ROS	16
2.5 Object Detection and Tracking in PMRs	17
2.5.1 Object detection	17
2.5.2 Multiple object tracking (MOT)	18
2.6 Future State Prediction of Agents	19

2.6.1	Predicting the trajectories of the robot’s surrounding dynamic agents	20
	Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM)	20
2.7	Social Navigation	22
2.7.1	Principles of social navigation	23
3	Overview of regulatory concerns in PMRs	25
3.1	Introduction	25
3.2	State-of-the-art	25
4	Predictive Collision Avoidance (PCA) for the TIAGo robot	27
4.1	System design	27
4.1.1	High-level diagram	27
4.1.2	Hardware specification	28
4.1.3	Software specification	29
4.1.4	Simulation task	30
4.2	System implementation	35
4.2.1	Pedestrian detection and tracking using image data	35
4.2.2	Pedestrian detection and tracking using 2D laser scanner data	36
4.2.3	Pedestrian trajectory prediction	38
4.2.4	Collision evaluation	42
4.2.5	Collision avoidance	45
4.3	Practical development process	47
4.3.1	Setting up the development computer	47
4.3.2	Development tools	47
4.3.3	Simulation setup	48
	Simulation tools	48
4.3.4	Pedestrian detection and tracking	48
	Pedestrian movement simulation	50
4.3.5	Pedestrian trajectory prediction	53
	Dataset preparation	53
	Training	58
	Evaluation	67
	Real-time inference	70
4.3.6	Collision evaluation	73
4.3.7	Collision avoidance	78
4.4	System real-world deployment	80
4.4.1	Open-source release and reproducibility	80
4.4.2	Deployment considerations in the TIAGo robot	81
5	Evaluation of the Predictive Avoidance Collision (PCA) system	83
5.1	Preparation of the simulation task	83
5.1.1	Creating a map of the scenario	83
5.1.2	Creating the global ROS node <code>tfg_launch</code>	84
5.1.3	Calculating the TTC of each scenario	85
5.1.4	Detecting a potential collision in the baseline and PCA configurations	86
5.2	Evaluating the system	87
6	Results	89
7	Temporal and Financial Costs	93

7.1	Financial Costs	93
7.2	Temporal Costs	93
8	Discussion	97
8.1	Objective 1 discussion	97
8.1.1	Results	97
8.1.2	Limitations	97
8.1.3	Suggestions for improvement	97
8.2	Objective 2 discussion	98
8.2.1	Results	98
8.2.2	Limitations	98
8.2.3	Suggestions for improvement	98
8.3	Objective 3 discussion	98
8.3.1	Results	98
8.3.2	Limitations	99
8.3.3	Suggestions for improvement	99
8.4	Objective 4 discussion	99
8.4.1	Results	99
8.4.2	Limitations	99
8.4.3	Suggestions for improvement	100
8.5	Objective 5 discussion	100
8.5.1	Results	100
8.5.2	Limitations	100
8.5.3	Suggestions for improvement	100
8.6	Objective 6 discussion	101
8.6.1	Results	101
8.6.2	Limitations	101
8.6.3	Suggestions for improvement	101
9	Conclusions	103
10	Future Work	105
A	Appendix	119

List of Figures

1.1	Examples of PMRs. (a) Amazon Scout. (b) Starship robot. (c) Waymo Driver. (d) DHL PostBot. [5]–[8]	1
2.1	PMRs on public areas. (a) A Serve Robotics robot on a sidewalk next to a person walking their dog. (b) A Mobinn delivery robot going up the stairs. [15], [16]	5
2.2	Applications of PMRs. (a) Food delivery. (b) Litter picking. (c) Snow removal. (d) Surveillance tasks. [17]–[20]	6
2.3	Cameras. (a) RGB camera. (b) Depth camera. (c) Thermal camera. (d) Stereo camera. [21]–[24]	6

2.4	LiDAR sensors. (a) 2D LiDAR sensor. (b) 3D LiDAR sensor. [25], [26]	7
2.5	Sensor images.	8
2.6	Simulation of the TIAGo robot in Gazebo. [56]	16
2.7	Overview of ROS-related images. (a) ROS logo. (b) ROS communication architecture diagram. [58], [59]	17
2.8	Example of object detection in a traffic scene with various classes: person, car, truck and umbrella. [60]	17
2.9	Example of multiple object tracking in a pedestrian street scene, showing the detected individuals with their assigned IDs and corresponding tracks. [62]	18
2.10	Typical architecture of a neural network. [65]	21
2.11	Architecture of a single cell of a RNN. [66]	21
2.12	Architecture of an LSTM unit. [67]	22
2.13	Data flow for an LSTM with multiple time units. [67]	22
2.14	Principles of social navigation for a socially navigating robot. [68]	24
3.1	Drafts of the ISO 4488 for comment. The ISO 4448 series under development addresses regulatory and technical frameworks for PMRs. Shown here are three draft components: TR4448-1 (Overview of Paradigm), TS4448-2 (Data Definitions), and TS4448-3 (Security, privacy, testing & data: Threat, vulnerability and risk profiles). [71]	26
4.1	High-level system block diagram.	28
4.2	Overview and components of the robot TIAGo. (a) Profile view. (b) Main components. (c) Frontal view. [74]–[76]	28
4.3	Software specification images. (a) ROS Noetic Ninjemys logo. (b) Ubuntu 20.04 LTS. [77], [79]	29
4.4	Representation of the ACAT in the simulation timeline.	31
4.5	Graphical representation of the determination of the TTC and CDT values using an example scenario. TTC and CDT are determined in independent simulations of the same scenario. The robot is represented as R , the pedestrian as P_1 and the robot’s goal as G . (a) $t_{\text{sim}} = 0$. (b) $t_{\text{sim}} = \text{CDT}$. (c) $t_{\text{sim}} = \text{TTC}$	31
4.6	Single-agent scenarios of the simulation task. (a) Scenario 1. (b) Scenario 2.	32
4.7	Multi-agent scenarios of the simulation task. (a) Scenario 1. (b) Scenario 2.	32
4.8	Cosine ease-in/ease-out interpolation function (blue line) with tangent at the midpoint (red dashed line) and a red dot indicating the midpoint. 33	
4.9	Visualization of the 4 trajectory categories. (a) Static. (b) Linear. (c) Interacting. (d) Non-interacting. [93]	40
4.10	Visualization of the 4 interaction types. (a) LF: Leader follower. (b) CA: Collision avoidance. (c) Grp: Group. (d) Oth: Others. [93]	40
4.11	System installation menu. [75]	47
4.12	Simulation tools. (a) Gazebo. (b) RViz. [53], [109]	48
4.13	Gazebo world used, named <code>car_1_junction</code> . [110]	49
4.14	Visualization of the “MA-S1” scenario simulation in RViz.	49
4.15	Animation of a walking human actor walking in Gazebo.	51
4.16	Two pair of cylinders representing two humans (each one with two legs). 51	
4.17	Plot showing the real-time position of the detected and tracked pedestrians by the <code>leg_tracker</code> module.	52

4.18	2D trajectory plot of the primary pedestrian and neighbouring pedestrians in an example scene from the <code>biwi_hotel</code> dataset file.	55
4.19	Distribution of scenes by data source.	56
4.20	Distribution of scenes by scene type (type I = static, type II = linear, type III = interacting, type IV = non-interacting).	56
4.21	Distribution of type III scenes by type (LF: leader follower, CA: collision avoidance, Grp: group, Oth: other).	57
4.22	Analysis of v_r in the <code>cff_12</code> dataset file.	57
4.23	Social LSTM model architecture.	58
4.24	Training time per epoch during the preliminary training experiment.	64
4.25	Training and validation loss over epoch.	67
4.26	Learning rate over epoch.	68
4.27	2D trajectory plot showing the comparison between the predicted and ground truth trajectory of the primary pedestrian in an example scene.	69
4.28	Example 2D trajectory of a pedestrian moving at constant velocity.	73
4.29	Visualization in RViz of an example collision detection when simulating the scenario “SA-S1”.	80
4.30	TIAGo access point configuration. [75]	81
4.31	Graphical representation of the network setup. (a) SSH connection between the development computer and the robot. (b) Physical drawing. (c) Logic drawing.	82
5.1	Bird’s-eye view of the map of the simulated world in RViz.	84
6.1	Comparison of the obtained ACAT values between the PCA and BL system configurations for each interaction type.	91
7.1	Gantt chart showing the temporal costs of the project.	95
A.1	Distribution by mean speed v_r in each dataset file. The histogram reports the number of scenes per 0.1 m/s interval of v_r	123
A.2	Distribution by motion direction–speed in each dataset file. The polar diagram shows the density of scenes by direction and speed, with the orange line indicating the median pedestrian speed v_r at each angle.	125

List of Tables

2.1	Sensors categories for PMRs.	9
4.1	Specifications of the movement of each pedestrian in each scenario. Each row specifies the starting position $(x_{\text{start}}, y_{\text{start}})$ and the corresponding goal position $(x_{\text{goal}}, y_{\text{goal}})$ in meters, and the motion duration T in seconds of each of the pedestrians in the scenario.	34
4.2	ROS node interfaces of the pedestrian detection and tracking module.	37
4.3	ROS node interfaces of the pedestrian trajectory prediction module.	41
4.4	ROS node interfaces of the collision evaluation module.	45
4.5	ROS node interfaces of the collision avoidance module.	46

4.6	ROS node interfaces of the <code>leg_tracker_sim</code> module.	52
4.7	ROS node interfaces of the <code>leg_tracker_eval</code> module.	53
4.8	Dataset files used in the TrajNet++ benchmark, organised by data source.	54
4.9	Description of the fields present in the the dataset files converted to the format expected by the TrajNet++ benchmark.	55
4.10	Relevant training parameters and their values.	59
4.11	Relevant training hyperparameters and their values (default values were used).	60
4.12	RunPod GPU catalogue showing the available models in the “Secure Cloud”, categorised by generation/vendor, with hardware specifications (VRAM, RAM, vCPU) and hourly pricing.	63
4.13	Summary of the evaluation metrics (ADE, FDE, Coll I, and Coll II) computed on the test set.	68
4.14	Evaluation metrics (ADE, FDE, Coll I, and Coll II) on the test set, categorised by scene type.	69
5.1	ROS node interfaces of the TTC estimator module.	85
5.2	ROS node interfaces of the costmap collision detector module.	87
6.1	TTC results.	89
6.2	ACAT results.	90
6.3	Statistical comparison of the obtained ACAT values between the PCA and BL system configurations.	92
7.1	Cloud computing costs.	93
7.2	Description of the tasks corresponding to each project phase as illustrated in the Gantt chart.	93
7.2	Description of the tasks corresponding to each project phase as illustrated in the Gantt chart.	94
A.1	TrajNet++: Statistics of the training split.	120
A.2	TrajNet++: Statistics of the validation split.	121
A.3	TrajNet++: Statistics of the testing split.	122

List of Equations

4.1	ACAT definition	30
4.2	Pedestrian motion equation using the ease-in/ease-out interpolation function $s(t)$	33
4.3	Normalised cosine ease-in/ease-out interpolation function.	33
4.4	Average pedestrian speed.	34
4.5	LSTM hidden state update	38
4.6	Sampling predicted position from bivariate Gaussian	39
4.7	Euclidean distance between the robot and pedestrian i at time step t_k	44
4.8	Collision detection based on safety distance margin δ	44

List of Algorithms

1	Simulation task evaluation process	35
2	Collision evaluation between the robot and the pedestrians	44

Abbreviations

ACAT	Available Collision Avoidance Time
ADE	Average Displacement Error
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AV	Autonomous Vehicle
BL	Baseline
CDT	Collision Detection Time
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
DBT	Detection-Based Tracking
DDP	Distributed Data Parallel
DFT	Detection-Free Tracking
DTC	Distance to Collision
DWA	Dynamic Window Approach
EKF	Extended Kalman Filter
FDE	Final Displacement Error
GPS	Global Positioning System
IDSC	Institute for Dynamic Systems and Control
IMU	Inertial Measurement Unit
IR	Infrared
KF	Kalman Filter
LiDAR	Light Detection and Ranging
LSTM	Long Short-Term Memory
MA	Multi Agent
MCL	Monte Carlo Localization
MOT	Multiple Object Tracking
NaN	Not a Number
NN	Neural Network
PCA	Predictive Collision Avoidance
PMR	Public Mobile Robot
PRM	Probabilistic Road Map
RAM	Random Access Memory
RNN	Recurrent Neural Network
ROS	Robot Operating System
RRT	Rapidly-exploring Random Tree
SA	Single Agent
SDE	Software Development Environment
SLAM	Simultaneous Localization and Mapping
TEB	Time Elastic Band
TTC	Theoretical Time to Collision
UKF	Unscented Kalman Filter
vCPU	Virtual Central Processing Unit
VRAM	Video RAM
YOLO	You Only Look Once

*Dedicat a totes les persones que s'esforcen cada dia per
superar-se i convertir-se en una millor versió d'elles mateixes.*

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Context and Motivation

In recent years, the mobile robotics industry and autonomous vehicles (AV) have experienced an exponential growth [1], establishing as key areas for technological innovation. In particular, sectors such as transportation, logistics and services have seen an increased incorporation of mobile robots. According to a report published by IDTechEx [2], it is expected that by 2044, the annual market value for mobile robots used in intra-logistics, last-mile delivery and mobile picking will be around US\$150 billion.

As technology improves, such robots are no longer limited to enclosed environments, such as factories and warehouses, and are increasingly being deployed in urban and public spaces. The potential of mobile robots in cities (formally referred to as public mobile robots, or PMRs¹) is broad and diverse, and include applications such as on-demand mobility [3], last-mile delivery, and express messaging services [4].

Some examples of PMRs that have captured the media’s attention include: the Amazon robot called Amazon Scout [5], designed for autonomous package delivery in residential areas; the Starship Technologies robots [6], six-wheeled robots for transporting food and small orders; the autonomous taxis of the company Waymo Via [7], equipped with advanced autonomous driving technology to offer driverless transport services; and the DHL PostBOT robot [8], an assistant robot that facilitates postal distribution in residential areas.

(A) Amazon Scout.

(B) Starship robot.

(C) Waymo Driver.

(D) DHL PostBot.

FIGURE 1.1: Examples of PMRs. (a) Amazon Scout. (b) Starship robot. (c) Waymo Driver. (d) DHL PostBot. [5]–[8]

Therefore, it is clear that PMRs will become an essential part of cities in the near future, transforming the way we think about urban transport and logistics. Their implementation, promises to increase the efficiency of travel, optimise the distribution of goods and contribute to the reduction of road congestion.

But this technological progress also brings with it a series of challenges that transcend the scientific and technical sphere and have a direct impact on society. On the one hand, one of the main social challenges is the acceptance of citizens and

¹See Chapter 2 for more information.

their daily integration [9], especially with respect to co-existence with pedestrians and other means of transport. On the other hand, ethical and legal issues arise, such as the regulation of liability in the event of accidents or the protection of privacy in the collection and use of environmental data [10]. Discussing these issues and establishing the regulatory and legal framework will be essential to ensure a safe, effective and beneficial implementation for society as a whole.

1.2 Problem Statement and Research Gap

At a technical level, safe navigation, correct perception, action in the environment, as well as correct adaptation to dynamic and changing spaces, are some of the key problems that need to be solved to ensure that PMRs can operate successfully in what will be the smart cities of the future [11]. Currently, one of the major limitations of most of these robots is that decision-making is based solely on information from the present, without taking into account possible future scenarios [12]. This limits the robots' ability to adapt to unforeseen or dynamic situations that may arise later.

Local path planners are fundamental tools for robot navigation, as they allow one to determine the best trajectory to follow taking into account the immediate environment [13]. However, these planners are usually based on real-time information and do not have the ability to predict the future movements of surrounding agents, which can generate situations of higher uncertainty and/or danger. To overcome this limitation, prediction of the trajectories of surrounding agents is presented as an essential tool to improve autonomous mobile robotics. The use of advanced prediction techniques and analysis of agent behaviour allows robots to be provided with a long-term vision, which allows them to anticipate possible movements of pedestrians, vehicles, or other agents in the environment. This predictive capability significantly improves the safety and efficiency of robots, avoiding collisions and adjusting their trajectory to ensure smoother navigation.

1.3 Project Aim

The proposal aims to demonstrate quantifiable performance improvements in PMRs by developing and deploying a new predictive collision avoidance system that leverages the forecasting of future trajectories of surrounding pedestrians.

The idea is to develop a general-purpose system, designed to be compatible and integrable on various platforms, and at the same time affordable in terms of computational resources, allowing for an efficient real-time execution without relying on high-power processors. Thus, the proposed system aims to overcome the current limitations of PMRs, advancing towards a new generation of robots capable not only of perceiving the current state, but also of anticipating the future, significantly improving their interaction with the environment.

1.4 Objectives

The main objectives of this project are:

1.4.1 Objective 1

Objective 1:

Detect potential collisions with pedestrians through trajectory forecasting.

Design a system capable of detecting potential collisions between the robot and their surrounding pedestrians by leveraging their predicted future trajectories. The anticipation of collisions allows the robot to adjust its navigation strategy proactively, improving both safety and fluidity.

1.4.2 Objective 2

Objective 2:

Achieve real-time execution with low computational cost.

Implement an architecture that performs trajectory predictions and replanning efficiently, enabling seamless real-time operation. The system must strike a balance between prediction accuracy and computational efficiency to be practical for real-world robotic applications.

1.4.3 Objective 3

Objective 3:

Validate the system in simulation in a methodological way.

Methodologically verify the correct performance of the PCA system within a simulated environment. The validation will use the Gazebo simulator to model the robot and pedestrian interactions, and RViz to visualise trajectories and robot behaviour. Successful validation in simulation provides confidence before deployment on a physical platform.

1.4.4 Objective 4

Objective 4:

Compare the effectiveness of the developed system against the baseline.

Evaluate the improvement achieved by incorporating the Predictive Collision Avoidance (PCA) system compared to the system with the baseline configuration. This will be quantified using a self-designed metric: the Available Collision Avoidance Time (ACAT).

1.4.5 Objective 5

Objective 5:

Prepare the system for deployment on a physical robot.

Ensure that the final implementation is not limited to simulation but is engineered for real-world deployment. Specifically, the system should be ready for integration on the TIAGo robot from PAL Robotics.

1.4.6 Objective 6

Objective 6:

Ensure compatibility with various robotic platforms.

Develop a modular system that can be easily integrated into different robotic platforms with heterogeneous hardware characteristics. This ensures versatility and adaptability, allowing the system to be deployed across multiple robot models and application domains.

Chapter 2

Related Work

2.1 Introduction to PMRs

As outlined in the Draft Technical Standard ISO 4448-2 [14], public mobile robots (PMRs) are ground-based machines, either autonomous or teleoperated, designed to navigate through shared public pedestrian areas without relying on visible human intervention or physical guides. Physical guides in this context refer to elements like rails, wires, or curbs. Although PMRs are not intended to require visible human assistance, they are still capable of:

- Being remotely controlled by a human operator.
- Carrying human passengers, such as in the case of automated wheelchairs.
- Being electronically connected to follow a human.

The main features of a PMR include its ability to operate alongside humans (and pets) in shared public spaces, such as walkways, sidewalks, bike lanes, parking lots, and areas in airports, hospitals, malls and transit stations (see Fig. 2.1a). Additionally, PMRs can be designed to board and move across platforms such as escalators, lifts, stairs or moving walkways (see Fig. 2.1b).

(A) A Serve Robotics robot on a sidewalk next to a person walking their dog.

(B) A Mobinn delivery robot going up the stairs.

FIGURE 2.1: PMRs on public areas. (a) A Serve Robotics robot on a sidewalk next to a person walking their dog. (b) A Mobinn delivery robot going up the stairs. [15], [16]

PMRs are diverse in their applications, including tasks like package and food delivery, automated passenger transport, maintenance services (e.g., sweeping, litter removal, snow removal), property surveillance and advertising, among others (see Fig. 2.2).

A key aspect of PMRs is their capability to operate in unstructured environments, often in the presence of unpredictable factors like blocked paths or poorly maintained

FIGURE 2.2: Applications of PMRs. (a) Food delivery. (b) Litter picking. (c) Snow removal. (d) Surveillance tasks. [17]–[20]

infrastructure. This is in contrast to industrial mobile robots (IMR), which typically operate in more controlled, structured environments where obstacles and risks are easier to manage.

Furthermore, PMRs are agnostic to their level of autonomy or reliance on artificial intelligence (AI). Whether fully autonomous or teleoperated, PMRs can operate across a range of operational designs, from fully automated systems to those that rely on human oversight or intervention.

In summary, PMRs are ground-based machines that can operate autonomously or be remotely controlled in public pedestrian areas without the need for visible human intervention or physical guides. They are capable of navigating spaces such as walkways, sidewalks and bike lanes, and can perform various tasks like transporting passengers or delivering packages. Their level of autonomy can vary, allowing them to function either independently or with some human oversight.

2.2 Key technologies in PMRs

2.2.1 Perception

Sensors

Cameras (RGB, depth, thermal, stereo):

Cameras are used for capturing visual information and serve multiple purposes, including positioning, obstacle avoidance and visual perception (see Table 2.1). RGB cameras (see Fig. 2.3a) provide standard colour images, which are useful for visual perception and object recognition. Depth cameras (see Fig. 2.3b) capture 3D information, aiding in positioning and depth perception. Thermal cameras (see Fig. 2.3c) detect heat signatures, helping in obstacle avoidance, especially in low-visibility conditions. Stereo cameras (see Fig. 2.3d) use two lenses to create depth perception by mimicking human vision, supporting both positioning and obstacle avoidance by detecting the distance to objects in the environment.

FIGURE 2.3: Cameras. (a) RGB camera. (b) Depth camera. (c) Thermal camera. (d) Stereo camera. [21]–[24]

LiDAR (Light Detection and Ranging):

LiDAR is used for visual perception —3D mapping and depth perception—, positioning —when utilised in SLAM-based localization—, and obstacle avoidance —detecting and identifying objects in the path of the device— (see Table 2.1). It works by emitting laser beams and measuring the time it takes for the beams to return, generating highly accurate 3D or 2D representations of the environment. Fig. 2.4a and 2.4b show a 2D and a 3D LiDAR sensor, respectively.

(A) 2D LiDAR sensor.

(B) 3D LiDAR sensor.

FIGURE 2.4: LiDAR sensors. (a) 2D LiDAR sensor. (b) 3D LiDAR sensor. [25], [26]

Infrared (IR) Sensors:

Infrared (IR) sensors operate by capturing infrared radiation, which is emitted by all objects as a function of their temperature, and converting it into an image or signal that can be analysed. This capability enables IR sensors to provide visibility in complete darkness or low-light conditions, where conventional cameras that rely on visible light would be ineffective.

Apart from visual perception, they are also useful for obstacle detection —particularly for identifying pedestrians, pets, or vehicles in environments with limited visibility (see Table 2.1).

GPS (Global Positioning System):

A GPS (Global Positioning System) sensor is a device that determines its precise location on the Earth’s surface by receiving signals from a network of satellites orbiting the planet. These satellites continuously transmit timestamped signals, and by analysing the time delay between the signals received from multiple satellites, the GPS sensor can triangulate its exact position in terms of latitude, longitude and altitude (see Table 2.1).

Accelerometer:

An accelerometer is a sensor that measures acceleration, which is the rate of change of velocity over time. It detects linear motion along one or more axes (typically x , y , and z) and can determine both the magnitude and direction of acceleration. By continuously monitoring these changes, an accelerometer helps detect movement, orientation and vibrations of a device.

Additionally, it contributes to positioning by estimating movement over time (see Table 2.1), helping to track a device’s location, especially in scenarios where GPS signals are weak, obstructed or unavailable.

FIGURE 2.5: Sensor images.

Gyroscope:

A gyroscope is a sensor that measures the rate of rotation around an axis and helps detect changes in orientation and angular movement, providing precise data on rotation and making it essential for detecting stability and direction. It also contributes to positioning (see Table 2.1) by improving the accuracy of tracking a device's orientation and movement.

IMU (Inertial Measurement Unit):

An IMU is a combination of accelerometers and gyroscopes used to measure and report a body's specific force, angular rate, and sometimes magnetic field orientation. It contributes to positioning (see Table 2.1) by providing data on the device's movement and orientation, helping track its position, velocity, and acceleration. It is essential for applications like navigation, motion tracking, and stabilization in industries such as aerospace, robotics and consumer electronics.

Encoders:

Encoders are used to measure the rotation of a wheel or motor shaft. Therefore, they can also be used for positioning applications (see Table 2.1) by converting rotational data into information about the robot's position.

Radar:

Radar systems can be used for both positioning and obstacle detection (see Table 2.1). They emit radio waves to detect objects and measure their distance, which is useful for navigation (especially in automotive and robotic systems) and for detecting obstacles even in poor visibility conditions (such as fog, rain or nighttime).

Ultrasonic sensor:

Ultrasonic sensors emit sound waves and measure the time it takes for the waves to return after bouncing off an object. They are typically used for detecting obstacles at close range (see Table 2.1).

Sensor	Visual perception	Positioning	Obstacle detection
Cameras	✓	✓ (depth camera)	✓
LiDAR	✓	✓	✓
IR Sensors	✓		✓
GPS		✓	
Accelerometer		✓	
Gyroscope		✓	
IMU		✓	
Encoders		✓	
Radar		✓	✓
Ultrasonic sensors			✓

TABLE 2.1: Sensors categories for PMRs.

Sensor noise and its impact on accuracy

Sensor noise refers to undesired variations in sensor readings that are not caused by the actual physical parameters being measured. These errors can be broadly categorised into two types. On the one hand, there is random noise, often modelled as Gaussian, which originates from sources such as electrical interference, environmental fluctuations, or the inherent stochasticity of the sensor's electronics. This type of noise is unpredictable and cannot be completely eliminated in software, but its effect can be mitigated through filtering techniques such as Kalman filtering or signal averaging. On the other hand, there are systematic errors, such as constant offsets or drift, where the sensor consistently deviates from the true value. These biases can typically be reduced through calibration procedures or compensation models. Both random and systematic noise can significantly affect the accuracy of the data collected, leading to errors in position estimation, obstacle detection, and overall system performance. Addressing these effects through filtering, calibration, or the use of higher-quality sensors improves the robustness of robotic systems.

Sensor fusion

Sensor fusion involves combining data from multiple sensors to estimate the state of a dynamic system. The resulting estimate is generally more accurate, reliable, available, and safer than estimates made using individual sensors alone. This approach can incorporate data from different sensor types. The core components of a sensor fusion framework include receiving measurements from various sensors, fusing them, and generating a single state estimate that can be utilised by multiple applications. By reducing costs, system complexity, and the number of components, sensor fusion enhances both the accuracy and reliability of sensing [35].

2.2.2 Localization

Localization refers to the process by which a mobile robot determines its position and orientation in relation to its environment. It is a crucial capability for autonomous systems, as knowing their own location is vital for them to make informed decisions about subsequent actions. In typical localization scenarios, the robot has access to a pre-existing map of the environment and is equipped with sensors that capture both the surrounding environment and monitor its own movement. The task of localization thus involves estimating the robot's position and orientation within this map, using the data obtained from its sensors [36].

The localization methods can be classified into the following categories [37]:

- **Route-based localization:** Involves guiding the robot along a predefined trajectory by using pre-programmed routes, which may include uploaded maps or physical markers placed within the environment.
- **Reference point-based localization:** Relies on detecting distinct features or tags that are placed in the environment. These systems use the identified reference points to estimate the robot's position. Examples of these use magnetic lines, RFID, QR codes and others.
- **Image-based localization:** Uses cameras and AI-based image recognition algorithms to estimate the robot's position by analysing visual features in its environment, allowing the robot to adapt to dynamic changes such as new obstacles or landmarks.
- **Acoustic-based localization:** Uses sound waves, specifically ultrasonic waves, to estimate the robot's position. Ultrasonic sensors emit high-frequency sound waves and measure the time it takes for the waves to reflect back from objects in the environment. By calculating the distance based on the time of flight, the robot can localise itself within the space. It is important to note that this method is typically limited to indoor environments.
- **Electromagnetic wave-based localization:** Involves various types of waves, including laser (e.g., LiDAR), infrared technologies, and radio waves (e.g., Bluetooth, ultra-wideband (UWB) and Wi-Fi). These methods are commonly used for both indoor and outdoor localization, offering varying levels of accuracy and cost depending on the specific technology employed.
- **Scene analysis-based localization:** This approach involves the use of signal fingerprinting, where environmental characteristics, such as transmitted signal power or other measurable features, are used as unique "fingerprints" for positioning. The robot's location is determined by comparing real-time measurements with pre-calibrated data of the environment. This method is effective in environments where signal patterns are stable and well-defined.
- **Odometry-based localization:** Odometry is a technique used for estimating the position and orientation of a robot by tracking its movement over time. It is commonly used in conjunction with motion sensors such as wheel encoders, accelerometers, gyroscopes and magnetometers.

Overall, most research in the field relies on probabilistic techniques to address the localization problem [38]. Probabilistic map-based localization approaches estimate the likelihood that the robot occupies particular positions within a known environment [39]. These techniques include a variety of methods grounded in probability

theory, such as Bayesian localization, which uses Bayes' theorem [40] to recursively update the robot's belief about its position based on sensor data and motion information.

One widely used approach is the Markov localization [41], which enables a robot to estimate its position even when starting from an unknown location by maintaining a probability distribution over multiple possible positions. It is particularly effective in recovering from ambiguous situations. The environment is discretised, typically into a grid or topological map, allowing the robot to update position probabilities based on previous states and odometry data. While robust, this approach can be limited by memory constraints due to the discrete representation of the state space.

Another common method is the Kalman filter-based localization [42], an efficient and precise method for tracking a robot's position from a known starting point, using sensor fusion in a continuous state space. It assumes that uncertainty can be modelled with Gaussian distributions, making it a special case of Markov localization. While effective in low-uncertainty scenarios, it struggles when the robot's belief is no longer unimodal—such as after collisions—potentially causing the robot to lose track of its position.

In cases where the robot's motion or sensor models are non-linear, the Extended Kalman Filter (EKF) is used to extend the standard Kalman filter (KF). The EKF is designed to handle non-linear systems by approximating the non-linear models with linear ones around the current state. While the KF assumes a linear system and Gaussian noise, the EKF makes these assumptions more flexible to accommodate real-world complexities. However, when the system is highly non-linear, the linearization used by the EKF can lead to inaccuracies or even cause the filter to diverge, resulting in poor performance. To overcome this, the Unscented Kalman Filter (UKF) was developed. Unlike the EKF, the UKF does not rely on linearization but instead uses a set of carefully selected sample points to approximate the state distribution. This method more accurately captures the non-linearities, making the UKF more robust and reliable in situations where the EKF might fail.

In more complex scenarios where the state space is large or the uncertainty is non-Gaussian, Monte Carlo Localization (MCL) [43], also known as particle filter localization, is often preferred. This approach represents the robot's belief using a set of weighted samples (particles), each corresponding to a possible position. These particles are updated over time based on motion and sensor data, allowing the method to approximate a wide range of probability distributions.

Each of these approaches offers different strengths and tradeoffs in terms of computational efficiency, accuracy and robustness, making them suitable for different types of environments and applications.

2.2.3 Mapping

Robot mapping is the process by which a robot creates a representation, or map, of its environment using data collected from its sensors. This map can be in various forms—such as grids, topological graphs, or 3D models—and serves as a structured way for the robot to understand and navigate its surroundings.

Mapping is a critical capability for autonomous robots as it enables them to operate effectively in unfamiliar or dynamic environments. Without a map, a robot cannot determine where it is, where it has been, or how to reach a destination safely. A reliable map allows robots to perform tasks like path planning and efficient exploration.

Below are the main types of maps used in robotics:

- **Occupancy grid maps:** These maps represent the environment as a grid where each cell indicates the probability of being occupied by an obstacle. There are two main types:
 - **Binary occupancy grids:** Cells are either occupied or free, represented by “true” or “false” values. These maps are memory-efficient but provide less detail.
 - **Probability occupancy grids:** Each cell has a probability value (e.g., 0 for free, 1 for occupied), offering finer detail.
- **Metric maps:** Metric maps offer detailed geometric representations of the environment, capturing accurate information about distances, angles and spatial positions.
- **Topological maps:** These maps represent environments as graphs, with nodes indicating key locations and edges representing paths between them. Topological maps are particularly useful for navigation tasks where relationships between places are more important than precise measurements.
- **Topometric maps:** These maps combine elements of metric and topological maps. They include precise coordinates while also capturing relationships between locations, balancing accuracy with computational efficiency.
- **Semantic maps:** These maps build upon traditional maps by incorporating rich contextual information about objects, surfaces and environments—such as object categories or material types—. This enables robots to understand their surroundings more like humans do, supporting advanced capabilities like object identification and navigation based on meaning or purpose.

Each type of map has its strengths and weaknesses, making the choice dependent on specific robotic tasks and environmental conditions.

2.2.4 Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (SLAM)

Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (SLAM) is a technique that allows a robot or autonomous system (e.g., drones, self-driving cars) to build a map of an unknown environment while simultaneously determining its position within that map [44]. This dual process is essential for enabling autonomous navigation in environments where pre-existing maps or GPS are unavailable or unreliable.

SLAM combines two fundamental tasks:

- **Localization:** Determining the position and orientation of the system in the environment.
- **Mapping:** Creating a representation of the environment based on sensor data.

SLAM systems rely on various sensors, such as cameras, LiDAR sensors, ultrasonic sensors and radar to collect environmental data. These inputs are processed using algorithms to detect landmarks and features, enabling the system to build a map and localise itself simultaneously.

SLAM methods can be categorised into several types depending on the map representation [45]:

- **Landmark-based SLAM:** The environment is represented as a map consisting of distinctive geometric features such as points, lines or poses (called landmarks). These are tracked over time and associated with sensor measurements to estimate both the robot's trajectory and the environment. This approach is computationally efficient and well-suited for structured or feature-rich environments.
- **Grid-based SLAM:** The environment is represented by an occupancy grid map. This method is particularly useful for robots equipped with range sensors such as LiDAR or sonar. It provides a dense and highly interpretable map, but can be computationally expensive if high-resolution grids are used.
- **Pose-graph SLAM:** The environment is represented by a graph, where each node represents a robot pose at a specific time. The edges between nodes encode spatial constraints derived from sensor observations or robot motion. These constraints reflect how poses relate to one another, either through movement or by observing the same part of the environment. Solving the SLAM problem then becomes an optimization task, where the goal is to adjust the poses in the graph to best satisfy all constraints, thereby producing a consistent trajectory and map [46].

Based on the estimation method, SLAM techniques can be divided into [45]:

- **Filtering-based SLAM:** In this method, SLAM is formulated as a recursive state estimation problem. The state includes both the robot's current pose and the surrounding map. A filtering technique is used to continuously update this state, incorporating new sensor data and motion information to refine the estimates of the robot's location and the environment [47]. One advantage of this approach is that the size of the state remains relatively small, making it computationally efficient. However, it also comes with some drawbacks: past estimates are discarded even if they were not yet accurate, and the overall precision of the method tends to be relatively low. Here, common examples of these type of filters are KF, EKF, UKF and MCL.
- **Smoothing-based SLAM:** This method estimates the robot's full trajectory using all the available measurements. Unlike filtering, which updates the state incrementally, smoothing optimises the entire trajectory at once, typically using least-squares error minimization. [46]. While it tends to provide more accurate results, it is computationally more expensive and requires more memory. A common example is Graph SLAM.

2.2.5 Path Planning

Path planning is a crucial aspect of autonomous navigation. It involves determining an appropriate geometric route from the robot's current position to its target destination while avoiding obstacles [48].

The goal of path planning is not only to find a feasible route, but also to optimise certain factors such as travel time, energy consumption and safety. It involves determining a suitable geometric path based on the robot's current position, its environment, and any constraints such as road conditions, terrain or dynamic obstacles like other moving objects.

Path planning is typically divided into two different temporal horizons [49]:

- **Global planning:** Collisions are avoided by considering the map of the environment and current observations. The path must be feasible, but not necessarily immediately realizable in real-time. It only needs to be a reasonable plan to reach the destination while considering obstacles and the surrounding environment.
- **Local planning:** Collisions are avoided using real-time sensor data. The path must be strictly realizable, meaning it must comply with the robot's inverse kinematic model. This ensures that the robot's movements, such as turning or moving forward, are physically feasible based on its capabilities.

Global planning

Global planning methods can be categorised based on the search strategy used to find a path from the start configuration to the goal configuration:

- **Unique search methods:** Plan a path for a specific start and goal configuration within a fixed environment. These methods typically build a search tree, expanding incrementally from the start point to the goal. A common example of this method is the Rapidly-exploring Random Tree (RRT).
- **Multiple search methods:** Allow planning paths multiple times from various start and goal configurations in a static environment. These methods create a roadmap or a graph, representing possible paths between different points. Once built, this roadmap can be reused for planning different routes, making it efficient for handling multiple planning tasks in the same environment. A common example of this method is the Probabilistic Road Map (PRM).

Global planning methods can also be classified according to the exhaustiveness of their search, which defines how thoroughly the configuration space is explored:

- **Sample-based methods:** The configuration space is randomly sampled and the search is based on these samples and the paths between them. RRT and PRM are examples of sample-based methods.
- **Grid-based methods:** The configuration space is discretised into a grid. The search becomes more exhaustive as the resolution of the grid increases. The number of cells grows exponentially with the dimensions of the configuration space. A common example of this method is A*.

The completeness of a method refers to its ability to guarantee a solution within a finite time or determine that no solution exists, depending on the method's nature:

- **Completeness:** A method is considered complete if it produces a solution in finite time or determines that no solution exists.
- **Probabilistic completeness:** The property that the probability of the method failing to find a solution asymptotically approaches 0 as the method continues to run. This is an important characteristic of certain sample-based methods. RRT and PRM are examples of probabilistically complete methods.

Local planning

The local planner or controller has two main objectives [49]:

- **Path following:** The robot must remain as close as possible to the predefined path.
- **Collision avoidance:** The robot must navigate its environment while avoiding obstacles.

In addition to these objectives, the local planner must account for the robot’s kinematic constraints. It is crucial to recognise that no configuration can be considered “perfect” in this context. Rather, following the trajectory often requires balancing the tradeoff between closely adhering to the path, maintaining operational efficiency and speed, and mitigating the risk of collisions.

Dynamic Window Approach (DWA)

A widely adopted strategy for local planning is the Dynamic Window Approach (DWA) algorithm [50]. DWA seeks to address the challenges of trajectory following and collision avoidance by evaluating potential control commands over a defined window of time. The process can be outlined as follows:

1. Sample in the robot’s control space according to the kinematic model.
2. Calculate the robot’s immediate future state by applying each sample. Discard collisions.
3. Evaluate each sample based on:
 - Proximity to obstacles.
 - Proximity to the goal.
 - Proximity to the trajectory.
4. Execute the one with the best score.

Time Elastic Band (TEB) planner

Another widely used local planner is the Time Elastic Band (TEB) planner [51] [52]. TEB transforms a coarse global path into a smooth, time-parameterised trajectory that respects the robot’s dynamic constraints. The process can be outlined as follows:

1. Represent the global path as a sequence of poses (position and orientation) and initialise time intervals between them.
2. Formulate a multi-objective optimization problem including:
 - Obstacle avoidance (stay clear of collisions).
 - Temporal feasibility (respect velocity and acceleration limits).
 - Path smoothness and shortening (avoid unnecessary detours).
 - Goal alignment (drive toward the final target).
3. Solve the optimization using sparse least-squares techniques to efficiently update the trajectory in real time.

4. Send the optimised time-parameterised trajectory to the robot controller for execution.

The result is a time-parameterised trajectory that adapts in real time to changes in the environment, ensuring both feasibility and safety. Due to its optimization-based nature, TEB can effectively handle narrow passages, dynamic obstacles and the robot's nonholonomic motion constraints.

2.3 Simulation Tools for PMRs

Simulation tools for PMRs are essential for designing, testing and validating robotic systems in a virtual environment prior to their real-life deployment. These tools allow developers to simulate real-world scenarios for tasks such as navigation, obstacle detection, and interaction with people or objects, minimising risks and costs associated with physical testing. These platforms typically offer realistic physics engines, sensor models (e.g., cameras, LiDAR, and GPS), and algorithms for motion planning, enabling robots to simulate tasks like pathfinding and dynamic obstacle avoidance.

Popular simulation tools include Gazebo [53] (see Fig. 2.6), CoppeliaSim (formerly known as V-REP) [54], and Webots [55]. These tools provide extensive libraries of robot models and environmental scenarios suitable for applications.

FIGURE 2.6: Simulation of the TIAGo robot in Gazebo. [56]

2.4 ROS

Most simulation tools are compatible with Robot Operating System (ROS), an open-source framework that provides libraries and tools for building and controlling robots [57]. ROS enables seamless integration of sensors, actuators and software components—such as perception, planning and control—making it easier to develop and test robotic systems.

At the heart of ROS is a publish-subscribe communication model. In this system, nodes (which are software components or modules) communicate with each other using topics, which act as channels for transmitting messages. A node can either publish data to a topic, making it available for other nodes, or it can subscribe to a topic to receive the data. This design allows different parts of a robotic system to exchange information without directly depending on each other, creating a modular and scalable architecture.

FIGURE 2.7: Overview of ROS-related images. (a) ROS logo.
(b) ROS communication architecture diagram. [58], [59]

2.5 Object Detection and Tracking in PMRs

The ability to detect and track objects gives autonomous systems real-time perception of their environment, allowing them to recognise moving and static elements that can influence navigation decisions. By maintaining a continuous understanding of the environment, robots can better react to changing conditions, reduce the risk of collisions, and operate more smoothly in crowded public spaces or other dynamic environments with multiple agents.

2.5.1 Object detection

Object detection is the process of identifying and localising relevant objects within sensor data, such as camera images or LiDAR point clouds. It enables autonomous systems to recognise their surroundings and determine the position of objects that may influence navigation or interaction.

FIGURE 2.8: Example of object detection in a traffic scene with various classes: person, car, truck and umbrella. [60]

In principle, object detection involves two core tasks:

- **Classification:** Determining the category or type of an object (e.g., pedestrian, vehicle, traffic sign) by analysing distinctive visual or geometric patterns in the sensor data. At a basic level, this involves comparing extracted features against known examples from a training set, either through predefined rules or learned statistical models.

- **Localization:** Estimating an object’s spatial position and extent within the sensor’s field of view. This is typically achieved by predicting a bounding box in 2D images or a region in 3D point clouds that tightly encloses the object. Localization ensures the system not only knows *what* the object is, but also *where* it is relative to the robot.

Several methods can be used for object detection, which can be broadly divided into non-neural and neural network-based approaches [61]:

- **Non-neural approaches:** These methods require the explicit definition of features that describe the appearance of objects, followed by an independent classification step. Common feature extraction techniques include Haar-like features (as in the Viola-Jones framework), scale-invariant feature transformation (SIFT) and histogram of oriented gradients (HOG). Classification is then performed using algorithms such as support vector machines (SVM) or other traditional classifiers. These approaches are typically more computationally efficient but less robust to variations in lighting, scale and point of view.
- **Neural network-based approaches:** These methods perform end-to-end object detection, learning both feature extraction and classification directly from raw sensor data. They are typically based on convolutional neural networks (CNNs). Some examples of these are OverFeat, the R-CNN family (R-CNN, Fast R-CNN, Faster R-CNN, Cascade R-CNN), You Only Look Once (YOLO), Single Shot MultiBox Detector (SSD), RefineDet, RetinaNet, and deformable convolutional networks. These approaches generally achieve higher accuracy and robustness in diverse environments but require more computational resources and large annotated datasets.

2.5.2 Multiple object tracking (MOT)

Multiple Object Tracking (MOT) is the process of continuously estimating the position and motion of objects over time based on sequential sensor data, such as image frames from a camera or successive LiDAR scans. It enables autonomous systems to maintain awareness of dynamic elements in their surroundings and adapt their behaviour accordingly.

FIGURE 2.9: Example of multiple object tracking in a pedestrian street scene, showing the detected individuals with their assigned IDs and corresponding tracks. [62]

In principle, object tracking involves three core tasks:

- **Association:** Determining which detected object in the current frame corresponds to which object in previous frames, thereby preserving object identity over time.
- **State estimation and update:** Updating the estimated state of each tracked object (e.g., position, velocity, orientation) based on the associated detection. Motion models are used both for predicting positions in the next frame and for handling short-term occlusions, ensuring that temporarily missing detections do not cause immediate loss of the track.
- **Track management:** Initiating a new track when a previously unseen object is detected consistently over multiple frames, and terminating a track when it remains unmatched for an extended period, typically indicating that the object has left the scene or is persistently occluded.

MOT methods can be broadly divided into [63]:

- **Detection-based tracking (DBT):** Also known as “tracking-by-detection”, this approach detects objects in each frame—using either pre-trained category-specific object detectors or motion-based techniques such as background modelling—and then associates these detections across frames to form trajectories. DBT is effective in automatically handling the appearance and disappearance of objects but relies heavily on the performance and generalization ability of the employed detector, often focusing on specific target types such as pedestrians or vehicles.
- **Detection-free tracking (DFT):** This approach does not rely on object detectors. Instead, a fixed number of targets are manually initialised in the first frame and tracked in subsequent frames using motion or appearance cues, such as optical flow, template matching or feature point tracking. DFT avoids dependence on detector accuracy but is inherently limited, as it can only follow the targets specified at the beginning and cannot adapt to new objects that appear later in the scene.

2.6 Future State Prediction of Agents

Future state prediction is a fundamental component of autonomous navigation, enabling robots to anticipate the evolution of both their own state and the surrounding environment over time. This predictive capability is crucial for safe and efficient navigation, especially in dynamic and complex settings such as public and shared urban spaces.

Future state prediction in autonomous navigation covers two main dimensions: the internal state of the robot and the external environment.

- **Robot:** This dimension involves forecasting the robot’s own future states based on its current motion model, control inputs and sensor data. These internal states may include position, velocity, orientation and, in the case of articulated platforms, joint configurations. Accurate internal state prediction is fundamental for reliable trajectory planning, control and proactive collision avoidance, enabling the robot to navigate with precision and safety.

- **Environment:** This dimension refers to the anticipation of changes in the surrounding environment, including static and dynamic elements such as pedestrians, vehicles, cyclists and other moving agents. Environment prediction typically leverages sensor observations, motion patterns and contextual information to estimate future trajectories of dynamic entities. Challenges include, for example, the unpredictability of dynamic obstacles, whose behaviour can change rapidly and unexpectedly, as well as environmental changes, such as adverse weather conditions or temporary changes in the environment (e.g., construction zones or emerging obstacles).

2.6.1 Predicting the trajectories of the robot’s surrounding dynamic agents

A particularly important aspect of predicting the future state of the environment is the estimation of the future trajectories of the surrounding agents. Accurate trajectory prediction allows the robot to anticipate possible interactions and plan safe and efficient manoeuvres in multi-agent scenarios. By leveraging advanced prediction techniques and analysing agent behaviours, robots can develop a long-term understanding of how pedestrians, vehicles or other dynamic agents are likely to move in the environment. This prediction improves both safety and navigation efficiency, allowing the robot to proactively avoid collisions and adapt its trajectory.

Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM)

To implement trajectory prediction, Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks have been widely adopted due to their capability to model temporal dependencies in sequential data. LSTMs are well-suited for trajectory prediction tasks as they can effectively capture the motion patterns and behavioural tendencies of agents over time.

Understanding how LSTMs work requires a brief overview of the evolution of neural network models for sequential data. At the most basic level, an artificial neuron is a mathematical function that receives one or more inputs, applies weights to them, and outputs a value through an activation function; each input is typically assigned an individual weight, and their weighted sum is then processed by a non-linear activation function to determine the output [64]. These neurons are the building blocks of artificial neural networks (NNs), which consist of layers of interconnected neurons, as Fig. 2.10 shows. While NNs are powerful in modelling complex relationships, they are inherently limited when dealing with time-series data or sequences, as they lack a mechanism to retain information across time steps.

To overcome this limitation, recurrent neural networks (RNNs) were introduced. RNNs [66] extend traditional neural networks by incorporating recurrent connections that allow information to persist across time. This architecture enables the network to maintain a hidden state that evolves as new inputs are processed (see Fig. 2.11), making it more suitable for tasks involving sequential data such as speech recognition, language modelling and trajectory prediction. However, standard RNNs have a limited capacity to learn long-term dependencies. In practice, they are typically trained using backpropagation through time, which can lead to the vanishing or exploding gradient problem [66]. These issues cause the network’s weights to become either extremely small or excessively large, severely affecting the model’s ability to capture

FIGURE 2.10: Typical architecture of a neural network. [65]

meaningful relationships across longer sequences. As a result, the performance of simple RNNs degrades in tasks that require the retention of information over extended time intervals.

FIGURE 2.11: Architecture of a single cell of a RNN. [66]

Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks [67] were specifically developed to overcome the limitations of traditional RNNs, particularly their difficulty in learning long-term dependencies. LSTM layers enhance information control through specialised gates that manage the flow of data between the hidden state, the output, and the future time steps.

Each LSTM unit consists of a memory cell, a hidden state and three key gates: the input gate, the output gate and the forget gate. Together, these components allow the network to selectively store, update and retrieve information, making it highly effective at capturing temporal patterns over long sequences.

Due to their reduced sensitivity to time lags between significant events, LSTM networks are particularly well-suited for analysing sequential data. The figure below illustrates the structure of an LSTM unit and how information flows through it at a given time step t . Each gate in the LSTM unit operates with its own set of weights and biases. The input gate determines how much new information is written to the memory cell. The forget gate controls what information is retained or discarded from the memory, while the output gate manages how much of the memory contributes to the block's final output.

The following diagram (Fig. 2.13) illustrates the flow of data through an LSTM layer in multiple time steps. In this configuration, each LSTM unit receives the hidden state and cell state from the previous time step, updates them based on the current input, and sends the revised states to the next unit in the sequence. The number of output channels produced by the layer matches the number of hidden units, ensuring consistency across the entire time dimension.

FIGURE 2.12: Architecture of an LSTM unit. [67]

FIGURE 2.13: Data flow for an LSTM with multiple time units. [67]

LSTM networks are especially well-suited, then, for pedestrian trajectory prediction due to their ability to capture long-term dependencies in sequential data. In such context, each time step corresponds to a position in a pedestrian’s path over time. By leveraging their memory cells and gated structure, LSTMs can learn motion patterns, anticipate directional changes, and model non-linear dynamics that are common in human motion.

2.7 Social Navigation

Social navigation refers to a robot’s ability to move through environments that include humans and other agents while taking into account the social dynamics of those spaces. It goes beyond just avoiding collisions or planning efficient paths—it’s about navigating in ways that are socially appropriate, respectful, and context-aware.

At its core, social navigation involves recognising and responding to social cues, norms and expectations. Intuitively, robots that move in shared spaces with humans are expected to be aware of how people behave, to interpret those behaviours correctly, and to act in ways that do not disrupt or discomfort others. This involves sensing (to detect what is happening in the environment), interpretation (to understand what those signals mean), and behaviour (to respond accordingly).

A socially navigating robot, then, is more than just a robot that moves—it is a robot that modifies its navigation behaviour based on its understanding of the social context-. According to [68], a socially navigating robot is defined as:

A socially navigating robot acts and interacts with humans or other robots, achieving its navigation goals while modifying its behaviour so the experience of agents around the robot is not degraded or is even enhanced.

2.7.1 Principles of social navigation

The core principles defined by [68] that a socially navigating robot should adhere to are the following ones:

1. **Safety:** The robot should always try to avoid hurting people, damaging things, or getting itself into dangerous situations.
2. **Comfort:** The robot's movements should feel natural and not make people uncomfortable. It should not get too close, move too fast, or behave in a way that could stress or annoy someone nearby.
3. **Legibility:** People should be able to tell what the robot is doing or planning to do just by watching it. Clear and predictable movements help others feel at ease and make it easier to share space.
4. **Politeness:** The robot should act in a respectful and considerate way, like waiting its turn or giving way when needed. It should avoid being pushy or disruptive, especially around people.
5. **Social norms:** The robot should follow basic social rules, like walking on the right side of the hallway or not cutting in line. These habits help it fit in better with how people normally behave.
6. **Agent understanding:** The robot needs to notice and understand how people and other robots around it are moving, and try to guess what they are going to do next. That way, it can move around without getting in the way.
7. **Proactivity:** If it looks like a traffic jam or an awkward moment is about to happen -like two people heading for the same narrow door— the robot should step in and help solve the problem instead of just waiting.
8. **Contextual appropriateness:** The robot should act in a way that suits the situation. For example, it might move slower in a crowded room or behave more formally in a quiet office than in a busy street.
9. **Responsiveness to context:** The robot should be flexible and adapt how it moves based on what is going on around it —whether it's navigating through a festival crowd, walking in a quiet park, or adjusting to local customs.

These principles serve as high-level goals for the development and evaluation of social navigation algorithms, ensuring that robots are not only technically competent but also socially aware and acceptable in real-world human environments. Fig. 2.14 illustrates these principles:

FIGURE 2.14: Principles of social navigation for a socially navigating robot. [68]

Chapter 3

Overview of regulatory concerns in PMRs

3.1 Introduction

As PMRs interact directly with pedestrians, cyclists, and other vehicles, significant regulatory gaps emerge. Existing traffic and sidewalk rules were not designed for them, leaving cities uncertain about how these devices should operate safely and fairly in public spaces.

Regulation in this context is not solely intended to restrict PMR operations. Instead, it serves to establish clear expectations for their behaviour, ensuring that they can operate safely, predictably, and in a way that is accepted by the public. Without a clear regulatory framework:

- Operators may face uncertainty about where, when, and how PMRs can be deployed.
- Municipalities may lack the means to ensure safety, accessibility, and equitable use of shared spaces.
- Existing infrastructure may not be designed to accommodate PMRs, as most current urban mobility spaces are predominantly designed around road vehicles. This creates inherent barriers not only for PMRs, but also for new mobility solutions.

Well-crafted regulation can therefore act as an enabler for PMR adoption, providing a common framework that guides both technical development and operational practices. By defining operational boundaries and behavioural norms, regulation helps to reduce conflicts, build public trust, and integrate PMRs smoothly into the broader urban mobility ecosystem.

3.2 State-of-the-art

Globally, the regulation of PMRs is still in its emerging phase, with most jurisdictions adapting existing regulatory frameworks for pedestrians, bicycles, or micro-mobility rather than developing specific regulations. To date, more than 25 jurisdictions have introduced legislation related to PMRs, often requiring that these devices follow pedestrian traffic rules when crossing roadways [69]. While these measures establish basic operational restrictions, such as maximum weight or speed, they rarely address more nuanced behavioural requirements that are essential for safe and predictable interactions in public spaces.

This regulatory gap is particularly clear in areas such as robot-human interaction, right-of-way negotiation and communication of intent. Unlike pedestrians, PMRs cannot rely on informal human signals, such as eye contact or gestures to indicate their next move. Without norms for such signals or behavioural predictability, pedestrians, cyclists and drivers may misinterpret the actions of PMRs, increasing the risk of confusion or accidents [10], [69].

Several early-adopting cities illustrate contrasting approaches to PMR regulation. San Francisco, for instance, initially imposed a near-ban on side-walk delivery robots due to concerns over pedestrian safety and accessibility, later replacing this with a controlled permitting system through its “Emerging Technology Working Group” to balance innovation with public safety. Toronto likewise prohibited PMRs on sidewalks and bike lanes following accessibility concerns but has explored pilot programs as a pathway toward more nuanced, long-term regulation [10].

At the regulatory level, initiatives such as ISO/DTS 4448 [70] seek to standardise the operational and behavioural requirements of PMRs, allowing legal provisions to be directly translated into programmable rules for autonomous navigation or teleoperation systems. These standards aim to bridge the current gap between software engineering practices and municipal legal frameworks by providing cities with ready-to-use regulatory references [69]. However, their adoption remains limited, and most municipalities have not yet aligned their local regulations with the new international guidelines.

FIGURE 3.1: Drafts of the ISO 4488 for comment. The ISO 4448 series under development addresses regulatory and technical frameworks for PMRs. Shown here are three draft components: TR4448-1 (Overview of Paradigm), TS4448-2 (Data Definitions), and TS4448-3 (Security, privacy, testing & data: Threat, vulnerability and risk profiles). [71]

In general, PMR regulation is still in its incipient stages, and most cities rely on rules adapted for pedestrians or micromobility. Current frameworks address basic operational limits but rarely cover nuanced behaviours that are essential for safe interaction. Emerging standards, such as the ISO/DTS 4448, offer a path toward consistency, but their widespread adoption is limited, leaving practical regulatory guidance for PMRs largely incomplete.

Chapter 4

Creation of a Predictive Collision Avoidance (PCA) system for the TIAGo robot

This chapter presents the creation of the newly proposed Predictive Collision Avoidance (PCA) system for PMRs, aimed at enhancing navigation performance. The implementation is demonstrated using the TIAGo robot as the deployment platform.

As outlined in Chapter 1, the goal is to develop a versatile and platform-independent system that can be easily adapted and integrated across different robotic systems. Moreover, the system is designed to be computationally efficient, enabling real-time operation without the need for high-performance processors. This makes the solution both accessible and scalable for a wide range of real-world applications.

4.1 System design

4.1.1 High-level diagram

To design the PCA system, this was divided into five key components or modules:

1. **Detection module:** Responsible for using the raw sensor data from the robot's sensors to detect pedestrians.
2. **Tracking module:** Responsible for monitoring the movement of the detected pedestrians over time, assigning an identifier to each tracked pedestrian and updating their position information.
3. **Predictive module:** Uses the tracked data to forecast the future trajectories of pedestrians. By analysing their past ones, this module applies an AI model to estimate what path the pedestrians are likely to follow in the near future.
4. **Collision evaluation module:** It analyses potential collisions by comparing the robot's planned path with the predicted trajectories of the surrounding pedestrians. Based on this analysis, the module updates the costmap of the robot's local planner by assigning a high cost to areas with potential collisions.
5. **Collision avoidance module:** Taking advantage of the updated costmap, this module allows the planner to replan the trajectory in response to potential collisions. However, its functionality is intentionally limited to trajectory replanning, as determining how to physically respond to an imminent collision is a much broader challenge that goes beyond the scope of this research. In such approach, the focus is exclusively on enabling the planner to autonomously readjust its trajectory based on the evaluated collision areas.

Thanks to its modular design, the system can be illustrated with the following diagram:

FIGURE 4.1: High-level system block diagram.

4.1.2 Hardware specification

The robot TIAGo, developed by PAL Robotics [72], was selected as the robotic platform for this project.

TIAGo is a mobile manipulator designed for research and development in areas such as navigation, object manipulation and human-robot interaction. It has been on the market since 2015 and is well-known for its stability, versatility and integration with ROS (Robot Operating System). The platform is compatible with ROS Noetic and ROS Melodic.

There are several versions of the robot available, including TIAGo LITE, TIAGo (standard version), and TIAGo++. Each version offers different features depending on the intended use, such as the number of arms, type of base or sensor setup. The robot can be equipped with either a differential drive or an omnidirectional base, allowing for flexible movement. Common sensors include a 2D laser scanner and an RGB-D camera, which support environmental perception.

TIAGo is designed to combine mobility, manipulation, and perception in one platform, making it a strong candidate for applications that require interaction with people and dynamic environments. These capabilities make it particularly suitable for evaluating pedestrian-aware predictive planning, where the robot must interpret the sensory data to build an understanding of its surroundings and respond to them in real time.

Among the robots available at the author’s university, TIAGo (standard version) was the most suitable choice given its features. The version used ([73]) includes a single arm, a differential drive base, a parallel gripper, and a laser range finder (see Fig. 4.2).

For more detailed information about the robot, its data sheet can be found here [73].

FIGURE 4.2: Overview and components of the robot TIAGo. (a) Profile view. (b) Main components. (c) Frontal view. [74]–[76]

4.1.3 Software specification

The system design process was guided by the requirements of the TIAGo robot platform, which determined the selection of ROS [57] as the middleware framework. Its modular architecture, extensive community support and widespread adoption in robotics make it well-suited for this project. Specifically, ROS Noetic Ninjemys [77] was chosen as the middleware version because it is the latest long-term support (LTS) release fully compatible with TIAGo.

The robot’s software stack is built on Ubuntu 20.04 LTS [78], the compatible Ubuntu distribution version with ROS Noetic.

(A) ROS Noetic Ninjemys logo.

(B) Ubuntu 20.04 LTS.

FIGURE 4.3: Software specification images.

(a) ROS Noetic Ninjemys logo. (b) Ubuntu 20.04 LTS. [77], [79]

Computational resources

The computational resources used to develop this project are as follows:

- **A Microsoft laptop:** A refurbished Surface Laptop 4¹. It was partitioned to install Ubuntu 20.04 and configured with all the necessary dependencies to use the simulation tools, code and deploy the system on the robot.
- **An Apple laptop:** A MacBook Pro (Apple M1 Pro chip)². The previous laptop is a high-performance computer, but lacks a dedicated GPU for graphics. This limitation affects the performance of the simulation tools. As a solution, this computer was used due to its high-performance integrated GPU for graphics rendering, particularly during system evaluation tasks. Instead of partitioning the hard disk to perform a dual-boot installation of Ubuntu, a Docker container [80] was configured and executed on macOS³.
- **GPUs suitable for AI workloads:** To overcome the local hardware limitations, cloud-based GPUs were used to train the AI model for pedestrian trajectory prediction. The details about the computational requirements of the GPUs and those finally selected are provided in a later section.

¹Specifications: Intel Core i7-1185G7 CPU, 32 GB RAM, 1 TB SSD, Intel Iris Xe integrated GPU.

²Specifications: Apple M1 Pro chip, 16 GB RAM, 512 GB SSD, 14-core integrated GPU.

³See Section 4.4.1 to read more about the Docker container with all the necessary resources to run the project.

4.1.4 Simulation task

Due to the limited scope of this project, testing and evaluation are conducted entirely in a simulated environment, allowing for controlled and repeatable experiments. Although the system is designed for real-world implementation and will ultimately be integrated into a real-world environment, conducting real-world experiments is outside the scope of this project. However, the simulation is designed to accurately reflect real-world conditions in order to ensure that the system will function reliably when implemented.

Simulation task formulation

In this work, the simulation task is formally defined to establish the conditions, variables and objectives under which the proposed system will operate and be evaluated. The formulation specifies the environment, the agents involved and the performance metric to be optimised. By providing a clear and concise mathematical description of the task, the subsequent implementation and validation are ensured to be both reproducible and grounded in a well-defined problem statement.

Consider an urban environment with a public mobile robot R equipped with a Predictive Collision Avoidance (PCA) system, and a set of N pedestrians $P = \{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_N\}$. The robot may or may not have access to a prior map and is assigned a goal G . The objective of the PCA system is to predict potential future collisions in order to maximise the Available Collision Avoidance Time (ACAT), thereby allowing the robot to replan its path as early as possible.

The Available Collision Avoidance Time (ACAT) is computed as:

$$\text{ACAT} = \text{TTC} - \text{CDT} \quad (4.1)$$

where TTC is the Theoretical Time to Collision and CDT is the Collision Detection Time.

These two temporal metrics are described as:

- **Theoretical Time to Collision (TTC):** The time elapsed from the start of the simulation until the moment when a collision would occur if both the robot and the pedestrian(s) maintained their initial velocities and headings without any avoidance manoeuvres. In simulation, TTC can be measured by running all agents simultaneously but without enabling physical interaction—treating pedestrians as *ghost agents*—and recording the time at which their predicted trajectories first intersect.
- **Collision Detection Time (CDT):** The time elapsed from the start of the simulation until the system first determines—based on the observed and predicted pedestrian trajectories—that a collision is likely to occur if no avoidance action is taken. During simulation, the system continuously monitors and predicts the future paths of nearby pedestrians; upon identifying a potential collision, the timestamp of this initial warning is recorded for analysis.

Fig. 4.4 shows a representation of the ACAT in the simulation timeline, and Fig. 4.5 provides a graphical representation of the TTC and CDT values in the simulated scenario, where the containing rectangle represents the walkway.

It is important to note again, as explained before, that the TTC is obtained from an earlier simulation run of the scenario (denoted as `sim_1` in Fig. 4.4). In the following simulation of the scenario (denoted as `sim_2` in Fig. 4.4), the robot detects the potential collision at $t_{\text{sim}} = \text{CDT}$ and then attempts to avoid it. The ACAT then is the difference between these two times and its value should be as highest as possible.

FIGURE 4.4: Representation of the ACAT in the simulation timeline.

FIGURE 4.5: Graphical representation of the determination of the TTC and CDT values using an example scenario. TTC and CDT are determined in independent simulations of the same scenario. The robot is represented as R , the pedestrian as P_1 and the robot's goal as G . (a) $t_{\text{sim}} = 0$. (b) $t_{\text{sim}} = \text{CDT}$. (c) $t_{\text{sim}} = \text{TTC}$.

Simulation task design

To evaluate the proposed PCA system, a set of simulation scenarios is designed to test and demonstrate the robot's capabilities across a representative range of interaction conditions.

Based on the interaction type, the scenarios are organised in:

- **Single-agent (SA) scenarios:** scenarios involving only one pedestrian interacting with the robot.
- **Multi-agent (MA) scenarios:** scenarios involving multiple pedestrians interacting between them and with the robot simultaneously.

For each interaction category, the following scenarios types are defined:

- **S1**: Frontal encounter in a narrow passage, where the robot and the pedestrian(s) approach head-on.
- **S2**: Pedestrian(s) crossing the robot's path perpendicularly, simulating an intersection with no visual obstructions.

FIGURE 4.6: Single-agent scenarios of the simulation task.
(a) Scenario 1. (b) Scenario 2.

FIGURE 4.7: Multi-agent scenarios of the simulation task.
(a) Scenario 1. (b) Scenario 2.

Simulation task theoretical implementation

Pedestrian walking was initially considered for modelling using a constant velocity model. However, an ease-in/ease-out technique was ultimately adopted, as it provides greater fidelity in representing natural pedestrian movement. When a pedestrian moves, they gradually accelerate from rest at the starting point, reach a near-constant speed around the midpoint of the path, and smoothly decelerate when approaching the goal. The ease-in/ease-out effect can therefore represent the characteristic acceleration and deceleration phases of human walking, resulting in a more realistic simulation of pedestrian motion.

The pedestrian 2D position can be modelled using the following equation, which incorporates the ease-in/ease-out effect by scaling the displacement in both x and y axes with the interpolation function $s(t)$:

$$\begin{cases} x(t) = x_{\text{start}} + s(t) \cdot (x_{\text{goal}} - x_{\text{start}}) \\ y(t) = y_{\text{start}} + s(t) \cdot (y_{\text{goal}} - y_{\text{start}}) \end{cases} \quad (4.2)$$

In this equation, x_{start} and y_{start} are the coordinates of the starting point, x_{goal} and y_{goal} are the coordinates of the goal point, t is the current time, and $s(t)$ is the ease-in/ease-out interpolation function. The interpolation is defined only for the motion interval $t \in [t_0, t_0 + T]$, where t_0 is the start time and T is the total duration. The function is normalised such that the motion always starts at 0 and ends at 1:

$$s(t) = \frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{2} \cos\left(\pi \frac{t-t_0}{T}\right), \quad t \in [t_0, t_0 + T], \quad s(t_0) = 0, \quad s(t_0 + T) = 1 \quad (4.3)$$

Here, t is the current time, t_0 is the start time of the motion, and T is the total duration of the motion.

The following figure illustrates a graphical representation of the cosine ease-in/ease-out interpolation function:

FIGURE 4.8: Cosine ease-in/ease-out interpolation function (blue line) with tangent at the midpoint (red dashed line) and a red dot indicating the midpoint.

The plot shows that at the beginning of the motion ($t \approx t_0$) and at the end of the motion ($t \approx t_0 + T$), the rate of change of the function is small, corresponding to gradual acceleration and deceleration. Around the midpoint of the motion, the slope of the function is nearly constant, approximating a linear progression, as illustrated by the tangent line at $t = 0.5$ s. This behaviour ensures a smooth and natural transition between the starting and goal positions, closely resembling realistic pedestrian movement.

As a result, designing pedestrian motion only requires specifying the starting position $(x_{\text{start}}, y_{\text{start}})$, the goal position $(x_{\text{goal}}, y_{\text{goal}})$, and the duration of the movement T . To obtain a quick estimate of the realism of the modelled motion, the average pedestrian speed can be computed as:

$$v_{\text{avg}} = \frac{\|\mathbf{p}_{\text{goal}} - \mathbf{p}_{\text{start}}\|}{T} = \frac{\sqrt{(x_{\text{goal}} - x_{\text{start}})^2 + (y_{\text{goal}} - y_{\text{start}})^2}}{T} \quad (4.4)$$

This expression allows verifying that the simulated speed is approximately consistent with the robot’s speed, whose default maximum value is 0.5 m/s.

Table 4.1 shows the specifications of the considered pedestrian scenarios, indicating the initial positions $(x_{\text{start}}, y_{\text{start}})$, the corresponding goal positions $(x_{\text{goal}}, y_{\text{goal}})$ and the motion duration T for each pedestrian.

Scen. ID	Ped. ID	x_{start} (m)	y_{start} (m)	x_{goal} (m)	y_{goal} (m)	T (s)
SA-S1	1	15	0	0	0	35
SA-S2	1	15	0	-5	0	35
MA-S1	1	15	0.45	0	0.45	35
	2	15	-0.45	15	-0.45	35
MA-S2	1	15	0.45	-5	0.45	35
	2	15	-0.45	-5	-0.45	35

TABLE 4.1: Specifications of the movement of each pedestrian in each scenario. Each row specifies the starting position $(x_{\text{start}}, y_{\text{start}})$ and the corresponding goal position $(x_{\text{goal}}, y_{\text{goal}})$ in meters, and the motion duration T in seconds of each of the pedestrians in the scenario.

Simulation task evaluation

The objective of the evaluation is to compare the performance of the proposed PCA system against two baseline configurations, assessing whether the PCA offers significant improvements.

The simulations are conducted using the following system configurations:

- **BL configuration.** This is the unmodified baseline setup of the robot, consisting of the standard navigation stack and planner settings provided by the default system implementation.
- **PCA configuration.** Our proposed Predictive Collision Avoidance system.

Let

- $S = \{S_1, S_2\}$ denote the set of scenarios,
- $a = \{SA, MA\}$ denote the scenario's interaction type.

The following methodology is designed to systematically assess the behaviour of the robot in each system configuration across all scenarios and agent types:

Algorithm 1 Simulation task evaluation process

```

1: for  $S_i \in \{S_1, S_2\}$  do                                     ▷  $i$ : scenario index
2:   for  $a_j \in \{SA, MA\}$  do                                   ▷  $j$ : interaction type index
3:     for  $\kappa = 1$  to 5 do                                       ▷  $\kappa$ : run index
4:       Perform a simulation of the scenario  $S_i$ .
5:       Compute the TTC from the simulation.
6:     end for
7:     Calculate the mean TTC by averaging the computed values from the
      previous 5 iterations.
8:     for  $\kappa = 1$  to 5 do                                       ▷  $\kappa$ : run index
9:       Perform a simulation of the scenario  $S_i$ .
10:      Obtain the CDT for both the BL and the PCA configuration.
11:      Compute the ACAT using Eq. 4.1, with the just obtained CDT
      and the corresponding mean TTC.
12:      Save the computed ACAT value.
13:    end for
14:  end for
15: end for

```

4.2 System implementation

Each module of the system was implemented through a dedicated ROS node.

The main focus of this thesis is the development of the predictive and risk assessment modules, aimed at determining whether incorporating pedestrian trajectory prediction can significantly enhance the robot's navigation performance or whether its impact remains limited. Consequently, existing turnkey solutions were employed for the human detection and tracking components.

4.2.1 Pedestrian detection and tracking using image data

Initially, pedestrian detection was implemented using an image-based method, using the YOLO (You Only Look Once) library [81], which is useful for real-time object detection, and the Deep SORT algorithm [82] for pedestrian tracking.

However, preliminary results revealed considerable latency, which hindered real-time performance and responsiveness, making it unsuitable for the intended application on the robot TIAGo.

As a result, the approach was reoriented toward a lightweight solution with lower computational requirements. Instead of relying on 2D imagery, the decision was made to only use laser scanner data, which is both faster to process and sufficient for detecting and tracking pedestrians in the robot's immediate environment.

4.2.2 Pedestrian detection and tracking using 2D laser scanner data

Following this change, the “Joint Leg Tracker” method [83] was selected as the most suitable option for detecting and tracking people. Several key factors influenced this decision:

- **ROS compatibility:** The method has been implemented in the ROS framework and was publicly released as a ROS package named `leg_tracker` [84], which is compatible with ROS Noetic —the selected ROS distribution to work with TIAGo.
- **Multi-person tracking:** The system is capable of detecting and tracking multiple individuals simultaneously.
- **High accuracy:** Preliminary results obtained when running the demo code demonstrated reliable detection of human targets using laser data alone. In such context, accuracy refers to how closely the detected positions of individuals match their actual positions, as well as the proportion of true positives —cases where a person is correctly detected— relative to the total number of actual individuals in the scene.
- **Real-time performance:** Preliminary results obtained when running the demo code showed low-latency processing, making it suitable for real-time robotic navigation.

Person detection

Autonomous person detection is performed through clustering [85] of laser scanner data, with confidence levels evaluated to reduce false positives [83]:

- **Data acquisition:** A 2D laser scanner captures distance measurements generating planar scan points.
- **Clustering:** Scan points are grouped into clusters using a fixed distance threshold that separates a person’s legs while avoiding more than two clusters per person (Euclidean distance-based clustering).
- **Noise filtering:** Clusters with fewer than 3-5 points (depending on environment noise levels) are discarded.
- **Egomotion compensation:** To account for the robot’s own movement over time (known as egomotion), the positions of detected clusters are transformed into the robot’s odometry frame. This ensures that observations from consecutive laser scans are expressed in a consistent coordinate system, allowing accurate tracking of people even as the robot moves.
- **Classification:** Clusters are classified as human or non-human using geometric features and a random forest classifier [86] trained on a large set of examples.
- **Tracking integration:** The method provides a confidence level (0-100%) for human/non-human classification, which is sent to the tracking module along with the cluster location.

Person tracking

Autonomous tracking is accomplished by combining a KF for motion prediction across consecutive scans and a Global Nearest Neighbour algorithm [87] to resolve scan-to-scan data association issues [83].

- **KF tracking:** All cluster positions are tracked over time using a KF that estimates both position and velocity. Tracks are created for each cluster and person, and updates rely on accurate laser scanner data and a constant velocity model.
- **Global Nearest Neighbour data association:** The system matches new detections to existing tracks using the Munkres algorithm, based on a distance metric that includes uncertainty. Unmatched detections create new tracks; unmatched tracks are carried forward. Person tracks are updated using temporary duplicates to handle leg-based detections.
- **Local occupancy grid map:** A local map is built using untracked scan clusters to mark non-human objects. This map helps prevent incorrect person-object associations and stops false person detections in known obstacle areas.
- **Person track initiation and deletion:** Person tracks are created only when two leg tracks move together, stay confident and are in free space. They are removed if confidence drops too low or position estimates become unreliable.

ROS node interfaces

The code implementation of this method is the publicly released ROS node `leg_tracker` [84]. This has the following relevant subscribed and published topics:

ROS node	Relevant subscribed topics	Relevant published topics
leg_tracker	/scan (sensor_msgs/LaserScan [88])	/people_tracked (leg_tracker/msg/PersonArray)
		/visualization_marker (visualization_msgs/Marker [89])

TABLE 4.2: ROS node interfaces of the pedestrian detection and tracking module.

- **Subscribed topics:**
 - /scan: Provides a `sensor_msgs/LaserScan` with the information from the robot’s 2D laser scanner. This contains an array of distance measurements (ranges) at specific angles around the robot. Each value represents how far an obstacle is in that direction.

- **Published topics:**

- `/people_tracked`: Provides a `leg_tracker/msg/PersonArray` message, which contains detailed information about each detected individual. Each consists of:
 - * A unique identifier for the tracked individual (`uint32 id`).
 - * The 2D pose of the person, where only the position is set; the orientation is not specified (`geometry_msgs/Pose pose` message).
- `/visualization_marker`: Topic used for visualization in RViz, where markers (`visualization_msgs/Marker` messages) representing the tracked people are published. These are helpful for debugging and for visually confirming the system’s performance.

4.2.3 Pedestrian trajectory prediction

To perform pedestrian trajectory prediction, the Social LSTM method [90] was selected as the most effective approach.

Problem formulation

The task involves predicting the future trajectories of the individuals of a scene based on their observed motion. Each person is represented by spatial coordinates at different time steps. Specifically, the position of the i^{th} individual at time t is given by (x_t^i, y_t^i) . Observations are available from time $t = 1$ to $t = T_{\text{obs}}$, and the objective is to estimate the positions for the subsequent time steps $t = T_{\text{obs}} + 1$ to $t = T_{\text{pred}}$. This setup can be treated as a sequence generation problem, where the input is a sequence of past positions and the output is the corresponding future sequence.

Method overview

The Social LSTM method uses an LSTM for each person to learn and predict individual motion patterns, with shared weights across sequences. To capture interactions between people, it introduces a pooling mechanism that connects neighbouring LSTMs, allowing the model to account for social behaviours in trajectory prediction (hence the name Social LSTM).

The overall method is structured around several key components that together enable accurate and socially-aware trajectory prediction [90]:

- **Social pooling hidden states:** To capture the influence of nearby pedestrians, the method extends the standard LSTM with a social pooling mechanism. At each time step, an individual’s LSTM receives the hidden state information from the neighbouring LSTMs within a spatial grid. These hidden states are pooled into a fixed-size tensor that preserves the spatial layout, allowing the model to compactly represent dynamic social interactions. The pooled tensor is embedded into a vector a_t^i , and the person’s current position (x_t^i, y_t^i) is also embedded as e_t^i . These two embeddings are then fed into the LSTM cell for that person, which is updated as follows:

$$h_t^i = \text{LSTM}(h_{t-1}^i, e_t^i, a_t^i; W_i) \quad (4.5)$$

Here, h_t^i is the hidden state of person i at time t , h_{t-1}^i is the previous hidden state, e_t^i is the position embedding, a_t^i is the embedding of the pooled social tensor, and W_l represents the shared LSTM weights. This equation illustrates how the LSTM integrates both individual dynamics and social context to produce socially-informed trajectory predictions.

- **Position estimation:** Given the hidden state h_t^i , the model predicts the person’s next position by outputting the parameters of a bivariate Gaussian distribution. This includes the predicted mean coordinates (μ_x^i, μ_y^i) , standard deviations (σ_x^i, σ_y^i) , and a correlation coefficient ρ_t^i that captures the dependency between the x and y axes. This probabilistic modeling allows the network to express uncertainty and represent multiple plausible future trajectories. The predicted position is then sampled from the resulting distribution:

$$(\hat{x}, \hat{y})_t^i \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu_t^i, \sigma_t^i, \rho_t^i) \quad (4.6)$$

During training, the model minimises the negative log-likelihood of the ground truth trajectory under the predicted Gaussian. The LSTMs are coupled by the social pooling layer, and back-propagation is performed jointly through multiple LSTMs in a scene at every time-step.

- **Occupancy map pooling:** As a simplified alternative to social pooling, the model can operate using only the spatial positions of neighbouring pedestrians, without incorporating their hidden states. In this variant, referred to as O-LSTM, each pedestrian i is associated with a binary occupancy map O_t^i , defined over a fixed-size grid $N_o \times N_o$ centered at their position at time t . Each cell (m, n) of the grid indicates whether another pedestrian $j \in N_i$ is located at the corresponding relative position $(x_t^j - x_t^i, y_t^j - y_t^i)$. This can be viewed as a simplified form of the social tensor, where each cell contains a binary indicator rather than a hidden-state vector. While this approach does not capture the motion dynamics of neighbours, it enables the model to learn reactive behaviours such as avoiding immediate collisions. Furthermore, since the occupancy map is computed independently for each individual, this variant does not require joint backpropagation across all trajectories.
- **Inference for path prediction:** During testing, the trained Social LSTM model is used to predict the future positions $(\hat{x}_t^i, \hat{y}_t^i)$ of each individual. From the observation period $T_{\text{obs}} + 1$ to the prediction horizon T_{pred} , the model iteratively replaces the true coordinates (x_t^i, y_t^i) with the previously predicted positions $(\hat{x}_t^i, \hat{y}_t^i)$. This enables the model to iteratively refine its trajectory predictions by using the previously predicted positions, which also help update the social context and the neighbouring information for each individual.

Method implementation

To use the Social LSTM method, this work leverages the PyTorch [91] implementation provided in the `trajnetplusplusbaselines` repository [92], developed specifically for the TrajNet++ benchmark [93].

TrajNet++ is a unified framework that standardises the training and evaluation of pedestrian trajectory prediction models. It introduces an interaction-centric benchmark composed primarily of scenes involving pedestrian interactions, using both real-world and synthetic datasets. Trajectories are categorised into four interaction types

—type I: static, type II: linear, type III: interacting, and type IV: non-interacting—enabling systematic comparison across models. Fig. 4.9 presents example visualizations for each of the four trajectory interaction types, while Fig. 4.10 provides additional visualizations illustrating the different trajectory categories within type III interactions.

FIGURE 4.9: Visualization of the 4 trajectory categories.
(a) Static. (b) Linear. (c) Interacting. (d) Non-interacting. [93]

FIGURE 4.10: Visualization of the 4 interaction types.
(a) LF: Leader follower. (b) CA: Collision avoidance. (c) Grp: Group.
(d) Oth: Others. [93]

Moreover, TrajNet++ also includes an extensive evaluation system that incorporates collision-based metrics to assess the physical plausibility of the predicted trajectories. These metrics support more accurate analysis of model performance, particularly in socially interactive scenarios. Additionally, TrajNet++ provides a wide set of helper functions (via the `trajnetplusplusptools` repository [94]), and synthetic and some real-world datasets (via the `trajnetplusplusdataset` repository [95]), thereby facilitating broader compatibility and ease of use.

To predict the future trajectory of a target pedestrian using the implementation of the Social LSTM method, this requires the observation of all the pedestrians in the scene over a predefined observation window. The input to the model is a sequence of (x, y) positions for each pedestrian over `obs_length` time steps. The model takes into account not only the trajectory of the target pedestrian (referred to as the primary agent) but also the trajectories of the surrounding pedestrians (referred to as neighbours), which allows it to model social interactions.

The trajectory predictions of the model are structured as follows:

- **Primary agent trajectory:** A $(\text{pred_length} \times 2)$ array of (x, y) coordinates representing the predicted future trajectory of the target pedestrian over `pred_length` time steps.
- **Neighbour trajectories:** A $(\text{pred_length} \times N \times 2)$ array representing the predicted future positions of N neighbouring pedestrians, where each neighbour's trajectory is also given as a sequence of (x, y) coordinates.

The `predict` function can return the previously described primary–neighbour pedestrian tuple for multiple *modes*, with each *mode* representing a different plausible future trajectory for each pedestrian. In this study, a unimodal prediction is performed, meaning that only one prediction is generated for each input. Such choice is intended to establish a baseline performance of the model without introducing the additional complexity of multimodal predictions (generating multiple predictions per input). Consequently, at each prediction step, the output consists of a single tuple containing the predicted trajectory of the primary pedestrian together with those of the neighbouring agents.

For the task of predicting the future trajectories of multiple pedestrians in a scene, it is not sufficient to designate one pedestrian as the primary agent and treat the rest as neighbours, since the Social LSTM method guarantees reliable predictions only for the primary pedestrian. Treating any other pedestrian as a neighbour may lead to inaccurate representations of their future motion, as the model’s dynamics are centred on the interactions of the primary agent with its neighbours. To address this limitation, the input matrix containing the observed trajectories of all pedestrians must be reordered so that each pedestrian is treated as the primary agent in turn. This procedure ensures that a reliable prediction is obtained for each individual in the scene while still leveraging the model’s social interaction mechanisms, thereby enabling the system to generate a consistent set of future trajectories for all pedestrians.

ROS node interfaces

ROS node	Relevant subscribed topics	Relevant published topics
traj_pred	/people_tracked (sensor_msgs/LaserScan)	/people_predicted_positions (traj_pred/AgentTrajectories)
		/people_markers (visualization_msgs/ MarkerArray [96])

TABLE 4.3: ROS node interfaces of the pedestrian trajectory prediction module.

- **Subscribed topics:**

- /people_tracked: Provides `leg_tracker/msg/PersonArray` messages, which contain information about the position of each detected person. Each message consists of:
 - * A unique identifier for the tracked individual (`uint32 id`).
 - * The 2D pose of the person, where only the position is set; the orientation is not specified (`geometry_msgs/Pose pose` message).

- **Published topics:**

- `/people_predicted_positions`: Provides `traj_pred/AgentTrajectories` messages. These are published at a frequency of 2.5 Hz and contain the future paths of the tracked people. The reference frame for the coordinates is the same as the one used in the previous module. Each message consists of an array of `traj_pred/AgentTrajectory` messages, which has:
 - * The unique identifier of the tracked person (`uint32 id`), which matches the input identifier.
 - * An array of poses of the person (`geometry_msgs/Pose[]`) containing the future T_{pred} positions.
- `/people_markers`: A topic used for visualization in RViz, where markers related to the predicted pedestrian trajectories people are published. These are helpful for debugging and for visually confirming the system’s performance. There are three namespaces:
 - * `people_spheres`: `SPHERE` markers representing the current positions of pedestrians.
 - * `people_labels`: `TEXT_VIEW_FACING` markers showing the ID of each pedestrian.
 - * `people_predictions`: `LINE_STRIP` markers illustrating the predicted trajectories of pedestrians over time.

Important note:

The sampling rate of the pedestrian trajectory prediction dataset was 2.5 Hz, while the publish rate of the `/people_tracked` topic was 10 Hz. To match the dataset frequency, predicted positions were published at 2.5 Hz. For simplicity, only one in every four position samples from the `/people_tracked` topic was considered. This approach ensured that both trajectories were temporally aligned.

4.2.4 Collision evaluation

To evaluate the potential collisions between the robot and its surrounding human agents within the future `pred_length` timesteps, the predicted pedestrian trajectories were compared with the future robot’s trajectory.

On the one hand, the future predicted pedestrian trajectories can be obtained by the previous module. On the other hand, to obtain the future’s path of robot, the path generated by the robot’s local planner was used. This is the immediate route the robot aimed to follow based on its current state and navigation objectives and is provided by the default active planner of the TIAGo robot, which is the TEB local planner [97].

The robot’s local plan is published to the topic `/move_base/TebLocalPlanner/local_plan` and consists of a set of poses (`geometry_msgs/PoseStamped[]`), starting from the robot’s current pose. Note that the timestamp in each message corresponds to the time the message was published, not the actual time at which the robot occupies that pose.

Robot–pedestrian future path synchronization

It was essential to ensure that both trajectories were temporally aligned as well as the coordinates were expressed in the same reference frame:

1. **Matching sample rates:** The sampling rate of the path generated by the robot’s local planner was required to match that of the predicted pedestrian path. In this case, the most restrictive sampling rate was that of the pedestrian path, which is 2.5 Hz (one sample every 0.4 s). Therefore, the sampling rate of the robot’s locally planned path was adjusted by setting the ROS parameter `/dt_ref` to 0.4, matching the pedestrian path frequency. This parameter describes the desired temporal resolution of the robot’s trajectory [97].
2. **Temporal synchronization of ROS messages:** To ensure temporal alignment between the messages from the TEB local planner and those from the pedestrian trajectory publisher node, the `ApproximateTimeSynchronizer` was used with a time slop of 0.05 s [98]. This tool is helpful for synchronising topics that may not publish at exactly the same rate, thereby allowing a consistent pairing of the planner’s output path with the corresponding pedestrian trajectory data.
3. **Matching coordinate reference frames:** The predicted pedestrian trajectories are expressed in the “map” coordinate frame, as described in the previous section. The robot’s local path is provided in the “odom” frame and must be transformed to the “map” frame to allow consistent comparison. This requires a rigid-body transformation consisting of a rotation and a translation:

$$\mathbf{p}_{\text{map}} = \mathbf{R} \mathbf{p}_{\text{odom}} + \mathbf{t},$$

where $\mathbf{p}_{\text{odom}}, \mathbf{p}_{\text{map}} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ are the position vectors of the robot in the “odom” and “map” frames, respectively, $\mathbf{R} \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3}$ is the rotation matrix, and $\mathbf{t} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ is the translation vector representing the pose of the odom frame relative to the map frame.

In ROS, this transformation is implemented using the Python packages `tf2_ros` (for handling ROS transforms) and `tf2_geometry_msgs` (for converting geometry messages with `tf2`).

Problem formulation

Let

- $p_r(t_k) \in \mathbb{R}^2$ be the robot location at the discrete time step t_k , where $k = 0$ denotes the pose immediately after the current robot position,
- $p_p^{(i)}(t_k) \in \mathbb{R}^2$ be the predicted position of the pedestrian i at the discrete time step t_k , where $i = 1, \dots, P$,
- $d^{(i)}(t_k) \in \mathbb{R}$ be the the Euclidean distance between the robot and the pedestrian i at the time step t_k ,
- $\delta \in \mathbb{R}^+$ be the safety distance margin threshold.

Each predicted pedestrian trajectory is compared with the robot's local path by computing the Euclidean distance between their positions at each time step:

$$d^{(i)}(t_k) = \|p_r(t_k) - p_p^{(i)}(t_k)\|_2, \quad i = 1, \dots, P \quad (4.7)$$

A collision appears if the computed distance is lower than a security margin threshold:

$$\text{collision}(t_k) = \begin{cases} 1, & d(t_k) < \delta \\ 0, & d(t_k) \geq \delta \end{cases} \quad (4.8)$$

Algorithm 2 Collision evaluation between the robot and the pedestrians

Require:

$p_r(t_k)$: robot's local path,

$p_p^{(i)}(t_k)$: predicted pedestrian trajectories,

δ : safety distance margin.

- 1: **for** $i = 1$ to P **do** ▷ for each pedestrian
- 2: **for** $k = 0$ to $T_{\text{pred}} - 1$ **do** ▷ for each prediction time step
- 3: Compute the distance:

$$d^{(i)}(t_k) = \|p_r(t_k) - p_p^{(i)}(t_k)\|_2$$

- 4: Evaluate collision:

$$\text{collision}^{(i)}(t_k) = \begin{cases} 1, & d^{(i)}(t_k) < \delta \\ 0, & d^{(i)}(t_k) \geq \delta \end{cases}$$

- 5: Compute the time to collision (t_{tc}) as

$$t_{tc} = (t_k + 1) \cdot T_{\text{step}}$$

where

$$T_{\text{step}} = \frac{1}{2.5 \text{ Hz}} = 0.4 \text{ s.}$$

- 6: Assign the point of collision (p_{oc}) to the robot position at that time step and:

$$p_{oc} = p_r(t_k)$$

- 7: Assign the distance to collision (d_{tc}) to the distance calculated before:

$$d_{tc} = d^{(i)}(t_k)$$

- 8: Publish the collision message containing the t_{tc} , d_{tc} , and p_{oc} to the topic `/potential_collisions`.
 - 9: **end for**
 - 10: **end for**
-

ROS node interfaces

ROS node	Relevant subscribed topics	Relevant published topics
coll_eval	/people_predicted_positions (traj_pred/AgentTrajectories)	/potential_collisions (coll_eval/ PotentialCollisions)
	/move_base/TebLocalPlanner /local_plan (nav_msgs/Path [99])	

TABLE 4.4: ROS node interfaces of the collision evaluation module.

- **Subscribed topics:**

- /people_predicted_positions: A traj_pred/AgentTrajectories message published at a frequency of 2.5 Hz containing the people tracked future paths or trajectories. The reference frame for the coordinates is the same as the one used in the previous module. Each consists of an array of traj_pred/AgentTrajectory messages:
 - * A unique identifier of the tracked person (uint32 id), which matches the input identifier.
 - * An array of poses of the person (geometry_msgs/Pose[]) containing the future T_{pred} positions.
- /move_base/TebLocalPlanner/local_plan: A nav_msgs/Path message containing the trajectory generated and optimised by the TEB local planner.

- **Published topics:**

- /potential_collisions: Provides coll_eval/PotentialCollisions messages. Each one contains the information about each potential collision:
 - * A unique identifier of the collision (uint32).
 - * The point of collision (geometry_msgs/Point message [100]).
 - * The time to collision (float32).
 - * The distance to collision (float32).

4.2.5 Collision avoidance

When a potential collision is detected, the robot must take action to prevent it. To achieve this, the collision avoidance module communicates with the robot's local planner to provide it with the information of the obstacle. It updates the costmap and recalculates the robot's path while considering such new constraint, ensuring safe navigation around the obstacle. In this process, a person is modelled as a cylindrical obstacle and published to the topic /move_base/TebLocalPlannerROS/obstacles.

It is important to emphasise that this module is designed only for trajectory replanning; determining how the robot should physically respond to an imminent collision is a more complex problem that lies outside the scope of this study.

Problem formulation

The task involves avoiding a potential collision point between the robot and an obstacle based on its current trajectory. Let $poc \in \mathbb{R}^2$ denote this predicted point of collision. A cylindrical obstacle of radius $R = 0.25 \text{ m}$ ⁴, centred at poc , is then published to the topic `/move_base/TebLocalPlannerROS/obstacles`. The TEB local planner uses this information to compute an updated trajectory that avoids the predicted collision. This setup can be treated as a trajectory modification problem, where the input is the robot’s current path and the predicted collision point, and the output is a collision-free trajectory.

ROS node interfaces

ROS node	Relevant subscribed topics	Relevant published topics
<code>coll_avoid</code>	<code>/potential_collisions</code> (<code>coll_eval/PotentialCollisions</code>)	<code>/potential_collisions</code> <code>_markers</code> (<code>visualization_msgs/MarkerArray</code> [96])
		<code>/move_base/TebLocalPlannerROS/obstacles</code> (<code>costmap_converter/ObstacleArrayMsg</code> [101])

TABLE 4.5: ROS node interfaces of the collision avoidance module.

- **Subscribed topics:**

- `/potential_collisions`: Provides `coll_eval/PotentialCollisions` messages. Each one contains the information about each potential collision:
 - * A unique identifier of the collision (`uint32`).
 - * The point of collision (`geometry_msgs/Point` message [100]).
 - * The time to collision (`float32`).
 - * The distance to collision (`float32`).

- **Published topics:**

- `/potential_collisions_markers`: A topic used for visualization in RViz, where each potential collision is represented through a `CYLINDER` marker. These are helpful for debugging and for visually confirming the system’s performance.
- `/move_base/TebLocalPlannerROS/obstacles`: Provides custom obstacles in the form of points, lines, or polygons, either in addition to or instead of the obstacles in the costmap (`costmap_converter/ObstacleArrayMsg` messages). This topic is used to supply obstacles to the TEB local planner, allowing it to account for them during trajectory optimization.

⁴The choice of 0.25 m as the cylinder radius is justified since the spacing occupied by a person is approximated as $2R$. A detailed explanation of this representation is provided in a later section.

4.3 Practical development process

4.3.1 Setting up the development computer

PAL Robotics provides an SDE (Software Development Environment) designed to simplify software development and deployment for programming TIAGo. This environment includes a customised Linux Ubuntu distribution (Ubuntu 20.04), the complete ROS setup (ROS Noetic distribution), as well as the necessary libraries, configuration files and dependencies required for seamless development and interaction with the robot.

The SDE can be easily installed on the development computer (the computer used to program TIAGo) using the USB drive provided by PAL Robotics (see Fig. 4.11). Once the installation is complete, the development computer is ready to communicate with the robot and equipped with the necessary tools to control, deploy software to the robot and test its functionalities.

FIGURE 4.11: System installation menu. [75]

Alternatively, the development computer can be set up manually by following the tutorial provided in [102].

4.3.2 Development tools

A ROS workspace named `catkin_ws` was created for the development of this project, containing all the nodes described in the previous sections, ranging from pedestrian detection and tracking to collision avoidance modules.

Several tools were employed to facilitate development, version control, environment management and code assistance, as summarised below:

- The code was developed mainly in Python language [103], using Visual Studio Code [104] as the Integrated Development Environment (IDE).
- Version control was managed using Git, with GitHub [105] as the remote repository for collaboration and code backup.
- Conda [106] was used to create an isolated Python environment and develop/run the code related to the pedestrian trajectory prediction module. However, when launching the full project, Conda was not used, as it is not fully compatible with ROS. ROS manages Python dependencies internally by relying on the system-installed Python interpreter and its workspace-specific package structure, ensuring that all nodes run in a consistent environment.
- Docker [80] was also used at certain stages to create container images for the project, ensuring that the software and its dependencies could run consistently across different machines and environments.

- AI tools such as GitHub Copilot [107] and ChatGPT [108] were occasionally used to generate code snippets, provide suggestions, and assist in debugging and documentation.

4.3.3 Simulation setup

Simulation tools

To simulate the robot, the tools Gazebo and RViz [109] were used. These were selected because they are the official, fully supported simulation and visualization tools for the TIAGo robot in ROS.

On the one hand, Gazebo is a simulation platform that provides tools, libraries, and cloud services for designing and testing in realistic environments, using open-source libraries [53]. It enables the simulation of a 3D world in which the TIAGo robot can interact with a custom-built environment.

On the other hand, RViz complements this by offering powerful real-time visualization of the robot's sensor data, state, and environment. In this project, it is used primarily to visualise the robot's relative position within the map, the goal, its local and global paths, costmap updates, and the positions of tracked pedestrians relative to the map, including their real-time locations and predicted future trajectories.

FIGURE 4.12: Simulation tools. (a) Gazebo. (b) RViz. [53], [109]

To recreate the scenario in which the robot performs its simulation task, a pre-configured world in Gazebo was selected. In Gazebo, a world is a virtual environment that contains all the elements the robot interacts with, including terrain, objects, obstacles, lighting, and physics properties.

For this study, the third-party world named `car_1_junction` [110] was used to replicate the urban setting described in Section 4.1.4. As shown in Fig. 4.13, the world features two perpendicular roads, three houses and a gas station. Both TIAGo and the pedestrian models move along the roads; for the purposes of this simulation, these roads are treated as sidewalks, since no pre-existing Gazebo world with dedicated sidewalks matching the desired urban scene was available.

4.3.4 Pedestrian detection and tracking

As described in a previous section (Section 4.2.2), the publicly released ROS package `leg_tracker` [84] was used as the implementation. This GitHub repository was downloaded locally and added as a ROS node inside the `catkin_ws` workspace.

After compiling the workspace with this new node and sourcing the setup file, the following command is executed to run it:

FIGURE 4.13: Gazebo world used, named `car_1_junction`. [110]

```
$ roslaunch leg_tracker joint_leg_tracker.launch
```

Once launched, the node starts detecting and tracking people in the environment.

Fig. 4.14 shows the visualization of the “MA-S1” scenario simulation in RViz. Each person tracked (simulated in Gazebo through two cylinders) is represented through a marker (published to the `/visualization_marker` topic) and assigned a different color based on their ID.

FIGURE 4.14: Visualization of the “MA-S1” scenario simulation in RViz.

Below is an example message published to the topic `/people_tracked`. This is timestamped and contains an array of the people tracked at that moment, with each person’s ID and pose:

```

$ rostopic echo /people_tracked
...
header:
  seq: 50
  stamp:
    secs: 23
    nsecs: 851000000
  frame_id: "map"
people:
-
  pose:
    position:
      x: 9.769220159002085
      y: 0.7069017504263365
      z: 0.0
    orientation:
      x: 0.0
      y: 0.0
      z: -0.9999270965487431
      w: 0.012074832818740435
  id: 10
-
  pose:
    position:
      x: 9.802095953744702
      y: -0.1885905789758547
      z: 0.0
    orientation:
      x: 0.0
      y: 0.0
      z: -0.9999423082508618
      w: 0.01074151618434069
  id: 11
---
...

```

Pedestrian movement simulation

In order to simulate pedestrians moving in the scene, actors were initially introduced. In Gazebo, an actor is essentially a model with predefined animations or paths that can move autonomously within the environment [111]. Fig. 4.15 shows an example of animation of a walking human actor in Gazebo.

However, the use of actors proved unsuitable for the intended purpose. They cannot physically interact with the robot—that is, they are not detectable by sensors such as the laser scanner, nor can they collide with the robot—. Consequently, while actors can look and move realistically, they do not influence or respond to the robot’s motion, making them inadequate for simulations requiring physical interactions.

For this reason, pedestrians were modelled as physical objects that could be introduced into the simulated environment and subsequently detected as moving targets

FIGURE 4.15: Animation of a walking human actor walking in Gazebo.

by the `leg_tracker` node. Each pedestrian is represented by a pair of cylinders, which serves as an abstraction of human legs, as illustrated in Fig. 4.16:

FIGURE 4.16: Two pair of cylinders representing two humans (each one with two legs).

These cylinders are defined with physical properties such as mass, height and radius, allowing them to realistically interact with the environment. The cylinder mass was set to 0.2 kg and the height to 0.5 m; these values are not relevant for the 2D laser scanner. The radius was 0.1 m, and the center-to-center distance between the two cylinders was set to 0.3 m. This configuration results in an effective spacing of 0.1 m between legs, which ensures that the `leg_tracker` node can correctly associate the two cylinders as belonging to the same pedestrian, since the maximum leg-pairing distance is set to the default value of 0.8 m (`max_leg_pairing_dist`). Additionally, the human representation corresponds to a resulting total width of 0.5 m, which can equivalently be modelled as a single cylindrical obstacle with a radius of 0.25 m.

It is important to highlight that the tracking confidence parameter (`confidence_threshold_to_maintain_track`) was intentionally set to 0, as the default value of 0.1 did not allow the system sufficient time to react and maintain person tracks. Setting it to 0 disables the confidence check, enabling faster detection and tracking, although it may increase the likelihood of false positives.

A ROS node named `leg_tracker_sim` was created to perform the simulation of the different scenarios designed in the simulation task. The main script implements the mathematical motion equations that describe the trajectories of the simulated legs and spawns the cylinders moving them according to these equations.

The user can select which scenario to simulate by inputting one of the previously described scenarios, identified by the IDs SA-S1, SA-S2, MA-S1, and MA-S2.

The following command is executed to run the `leg_tracker_sim` node, after compiling the workspace with this new node and sourcing the setup file:

```
$ rosrn leg_tracker_sim leg_tracker_sim.py --scenario_id
  <scenario_id>
```

This node publishes the real-time position or ground-truth positions of the pedestrians:

ROS node	Published topics
leg_tracker_sim	/people_positions (PersonArray)
	/people_positions_markers (MarkerArray [96])

TABLE 4.6: ROS node interfaces of the `leg_tracker_sim` module.

Additionally, to check that the `leg_tracker` node is accurately detecting and tracking the pedestrians in the scene, a real-time plot was added to show the positions that are being estimated versus the ground-truth trajectories generated by the `leg_tracker_sim` node, as shown in Fig. 4.17:

FIGURE 4.17: Plot showing the real-time position of the detected and tracked pedestrians by the `leg_tracker` module.

A person is considered correctly detected when their position is estimated to be in the middle between their two legs. The difference between this estimated position and the true position represents the estimation error, which serves as a direct measure of the system's accuracy. This error is calculated as the Euclidean distance between the estimated position and the corresponding ground-truth position.

For this purpose, a dedicated ROS node called `leg_tracker_eval` was created. This node evaluates how accurately the `leg_tracker` module detects people by comparing the detected positions with the expected ground-truth positions. After compiling the workspace with this new node and sourcing the setup file, the following command is executed to run the `leg_tracker_eval` node:

```
$ rosrn leg_tracker_eval leg_tracker_eval.py
```

Table 4.7 lists the subscribed topics of the `leg_tracker_eval` node:

ROS node	Subscribed topics
leg_tracker_eval	/people_positions (PersonArray)
	/people_tracked (PersonArray)

TABLE 4.7: ROS node interfaces of the `leg_tracker_eval` module.

4.3.5 Pedestrian trajectory prediction

As outlined in a previous section (Section 4.2.3), this work builds upon the PyTorch implementation of the Social LSTM method available in the `trajnetplusplusbaselines` repository [92], which is complemented by the `trajnetplusplusdataset` [95] and `trajnetplusplustools` [94] repositories.

As no suitable pre-trained model was available, it was necessary to build a custom one. This section describes the entire process, covering all phases, including dataset preparation, model training, and evaluation.

Dataset preparation

1. Dataset selection

With the will to reproduce the results reported in the baseline paper [112], the same dataset files were used. These are listed below in Table 4.8, with their corresponding data sources and a short description of each.

However, it was not possible to replicate the exact training, validation and test splits because this information was not provided in the paper.

After analysing the dataset structure (see Tables A.1, A.2, A.3 listed in the Appendix A), it was observed that the amount of data differed from what was reported in the “Supplementary Material” of the reference paper [112]. This discrepancy could not be fully explained and was further compounded by the absence of the `cff` family, `lcas` and `wildtrack` dataset files in the `trajnetplusplusdataset` GitHub repository [95], which had to be obtained by searching on the Internet their original sources.

After several hours, the datasets were successfully found, downloaded and extracted in the folder `trajnetplusplusdataset/data/raw` [123].

It is worth restating that the focus of this project is therefore on developing a functional system, and it is acknowledged that a direct and fully fair comparison with the baseline paper cannot be performed. To achieve a fair comparison, results should ideally be submitted to the challenge opened by the authors on AICrowd [124];

Data source	Dataset files	Description
BIWI Walking Pedestrians (EWAP) [113], [114]	biwi_eth, biwi_hotel	Manually annotated pedestrian trajectories in crowded outdoor scenes, captured from a bird’s-eye view at the top of the main building of the university ETH Zurich and at a hotel entrance in Zurich (Switzerland).
UCY [115], [116]	crowds_students001, crowds_students003, crowds_zara01, crowds_zara02, crowds_zara03, uni_examples	Manually annotated pedestrian trajectories in crowded outdoor scenes, captured from a bird’s-eye view at the University of Cyprus campus and in front of a Zara store in Nicosia (Cyprus).
CFE [117], [118]	cff_06, cff_07, cff_08, cff_09, cff_10, cff_12, cff_13, cff_14, cff_15, cff_16, cff_17, cff_18	Pedestrian trajectories automatically extracted from crowded scenes in train stations, recorded with a dense network of more than 100 cameras (optical, thermal and RGB-D), resulting in over 42 million trajectories.
WILDTRACK [119], [120]	wildtrack	Manually annotated pedestrian trajectories in crowded outdoor scenes, captured with seven statically positioned HD cameras in front of the main building of the university ETH Zurich in Switzerland.
L-CAS [121], [122]	lcas	Automatically extracted pedestrian trajectories recorded with a 3D LiDAR sensor mounted on a mobile robot in one of the main buildings of the University of Lincoln (UK).

TABLE 4.8: Dataset files used in the TrajNet++ benchmark, organised by data source.

however, this is beyond the scope of the project.

2. Dataset conversion

The dataset files were first converted into the format required by the Trajnet++ benchmark using the following command:

```
$ python -m trajnetdataset.convert
```

Executing this script generates an output directory containing four subfolders: `train`, `val`, `test`, and `test_private`⁵. The data were divided into 60 % for training, 20 % for validation and the remaining 20 % for testing.

Each folder contains `.ndjson` files, in which each line represents a different scene. An example of a scene is shown below:

⁵The `test_private` set contains the ground-truth trajectories corresponding to the test set.

```
"scene": "id": 77740, "p": 8196, "s": 47172, "e": 47252, "fps":
2.5, "tag": 0
```

Table 4.9 shows the description of each of the fields present in the `.ndjson` files:

Field	Description
<code>id</code>	ID of the scene.
<code>p</code>	ID of the pedestrian.
<code>s</code>	Frame index of the first observation of pedestrian “p” in the scene.
<code>e</code>	Frame index of the last observation of pedestrian “p” in the scene.
<code>fps</code>	Frame rate of the scene.
<code>tag</code>	Trajectory interaction type (1 = type I, 2 = type II, 3 = type III, 4 = type IV).

TABLE 4.9: Description of the fields present in the the dataset files converted to the format expected by the TrajNet++ benchmark.

Fig. 4.18 shows the 2D trajectory plot of an example scene from the `biwi_hotel` dataset file. The primary pedestrian is represented with a continuous line, the neighbouring pedestrians with dashed lines, and the starting and ending positions with a cross and a dot mark, respectively.

FIGURE 4.18: 2D trajectory plot of the primary pedestrian and neighbouring pedestrians in an example scene from the `biwi_hotel` dataset file.

3. Dataset analysis

To better understand the data and its internal composition, the available helper functions in the `trajnetplusplus` repository were used to obtain the following information:

- **Distribution by data source:** Fig. 4.19 shows the distribution of scenes by data source. It can be observed that the `cff` dataset family is predominant, representing 97.7 % of the entire dataset, whereas each of the other sources account for approximately 1 % or less.

FIGURE 4.19: Distribution of scenes by data source.

- **Distribution by scene type:** As shown in Fig. 4.20, the distribution of scenes is similar across the three splits (training, validation and test). Type III interactions are predominant, which is beneficial as they are interactive. Type II interactions (linear) are the next most common, followed by a small proportion of Type IV interactions (non-interacting). Type I interactions (static) are the least frequent (< 1 %), which is favourable since they are static.

FIGURE 4.20: Distribution of scenes by scene type (type I = static, type II = linear, type III = interacting, type IV = non-interacting).

- **Distribution by mean speed v_r :** v_r denotes the mean pedestrian speed in a scene. Fig. A.1 in the Appendix A shows a histogram of v_r in each dataset file, showing the number of scenes for each 0.1 m/s interval of v_r . In all cases, v_r spans the range from 0 to 2.5 m/s. Since the `cff` family is predominant in the dataset (as shown in Fig. 4.19), the overall distribution of v_r largely reflects the behaviour of this family, which is consistent across its dataset files. A representative example of this behaviour can be shown through the `cff_12`

FIGURE 4.21: Distribution of type III scenes by type (LF: leader follower, CA: collision avoidance, Grp: group, Oth: other).

dataset file in Fig. 4.22a. This shows that the frequency of speeds increases approximately linearly up to 1.25 m/s. The mode occurs between 1.3 and 1.4 m/s, after which the frequency declines in an almost exponential manner.

- **Distribution by motion direction–speed:** Fig. A.2 in Appendix A presents a polar diagram for each dataset file, illustrating the distribution of scenes by motion direction (angle) and speed (radius). In the diagram, darker blue indicates higher scene density within a specific motion direction–speed region, while the orange line represents the median v_r associated with that angle. The `cff` family clearly represents the most comprehensive dataset, as it includes pedestrians moving in all directions (0° to 360°) and exhibits a more diverse range of speeds v_r compared to the other datasets. In contrast, pedestrian movement in the other datasets is largely restricted to the front, with directions concentrated around 0° and many directions under-represented. The predominance of the `cff` family is advantageous due to the completeness it brings to the dataset. An illustrative example of the pattern followed by the full dataset can be shown through the `cff_12` dataset file in Fig. 4.22b.

(A) Distribution by mean speed v_r . The histogram reports the number of scenes per 0.1 m/s interval of v_r .

(B) Distribution by motion direction–speed. The polar diagram shows the density of scenes by direction and speed, with the orange line indicating the median pedestrian speed v_r at each angle.

FIGURE 4.22: Analysis of v_r in the `cff_12` dataset file.

Training

1. Model architecture

The architecture of the trained model was obtained using the `summary` function from the `torchinfo` library [125]. This tool provides a layer-by-layer overview of the network, including the input and output shapes, number of parameters and trainable status of each layer.

Fig. 4.23 illustrates the model architecture, which corresponds to the description provided earlier in Section 4.2.3.

FIGURE 4.23: Social LSTM model architecture.

The Social LSTM method models pedestrians trajectories in a scene by assigning one LSTM to each one. Each LSTM learns the state of its pedestrian and predicts its future position. Since independent LSTMs cannot capture interactions between multiple pedestrians, the model introduces a social pooling mechanism that shares information across neighbouring pedestrians.

Concretely, the observed position of the i -th pedestrian at time t , denoted as \mathbf{x}_t^i , is first mapped into a 64-dimensional representation via a linear embedding layer followed by a ReLU activation function [126] (**InputEmbedding** node).

Neighbour interactions are then encoded by a grid-based pooling layer (**GridBased Pooling** node), which projects neighbour features through a linear layer, arranges them into a spatial grid, and embeds the grid representation via a linear layer followed by a ReLU activation function (256-dim).

The concatenated embedding and pooled features are then passed into an LSTM cell (**LSTMCell** node) with hidden size $h = 128$, which updates the hidden state \mathbf{h}_t . In this way, the LSTM at each time step incorporates both the individual trajectory history and the influence of the nearby pedestrians.

Finally, a linear output layer (`Hidden2Normal` node) maps the hidden state \mathbf{h}_t^i to a bivariate Gaussian distribution describing the predicted position. This distribution is parametrised by the 5-dimensional output vector $(\mu_x, \mu_y, \sigma_x, \sigma_y, \rho)$.

It is worth restating that the parameters of the LSTM model are optimised by minimising the negative log-likelihood loss over all the trajectories in the training dataset.

2. Parameters & hyperparameters selection

With the goal of reproducing the results reported in the baseline paper [112], the model was trained using the same parameters and hyperparameters.

Among the training parameters, particular attention should be paid to `pred_length` and `obs_length`, as they determine the temporal horizons of prediction and observation, respectively. Specifically, these parameters define the duration over which pedestrian trajectories are observed before forecasting and the time span into the future for which predictions are generated. Their initial values of 12 and 9, respectively, were proportionally reduced by one-third to 8 and 6 to decrease the observation and prediction time windows, enabling real-time execution.

Assuming a temporal resolution of $T_{\text{step}} = 0.4$ s, the prediction horizon corresponding to `pred_length` = 8 is

$$\text{pred_length} \times T_{\text{step}} = 8 \times 0.4 = 3.2 \text{ seconds.}$$

Analogously, with an observation length of `obs_length` = 6, the observation horizon is

$$\text{obs_length} \times T_{\text{step}} = 6 \times 0.4 = 2.4 \text{ seconds.}$$

The number of training epochs is 25, and a checkpoint is saved every 5 epochs. This ensures that, in case of an interruption, training can resume from the last checkpoint without losing progress.

The remaining training parameters and hyperparameters are summarised in Tables 4.10 and 4.11:

Parameter	Description	Value
<code>epochs</code>	Number of training epochs.	25
<code>obs_length</code>	Number of observation frames used to predict a pedestrian trajectory.	6
<code>pred_length</code>	Number of future frames to predict from the observed trajectory.	8
<code>save_every</code>	Interval (in epochs) at which model checkpoints are saved.	5
<code>seed</code>	Random seed for reproducibility.	42
<code>start_length</code>	Index of the first frame used for the observation window (relative to the trajectory start).	0
<code>step_size</code>	Step size for the learning rate scheduler.	10
<code>type</code>	Type of interaction encoder.	"social"

TABLE 4.10: Relevant training parameters and their values.

Hyperparameter	Description	Default value
augment	Perform rotation augmentation on the dataset.	False
augment_noise	Add noise to observed trajectories during training to improve robustness.	False
batch_size	Batch size.	8
cell_side	Interaction module layer dimensions (grid-based pooling).	0.6
col_distance	Distance threshold for collision occurrence.	0.2
col_wt	Collision loss weight.	0.0
coordinate-embedding-dim	Coordinate embedding dimension.	64
embedding_arch	Interaction encoding architecture (grid-based pooling).	"one_layer"
front	Flag to only consider pedestrians in front (grid-based pooling).	False
hidden-dim	LSTM hidden dimension.	128
latent_dim	Latent dimension of the encoder hidden state used in social pooling.	16
layer_dims	Interaction module layer dimensions (grid-based pooling).	[512]
loss	Loss objective: choice between L2 ("L2") or Gaussian negative log-likelihood ("pred").	"pred"
lr	Initial learning rate.	1e-3
n	Number of cells per side (grid-based pooling).	12
normalize_scene	Normalize trajectories by rotating the scene so that the primary pedestrian moves northwards at the end of the observation.	False
pool_constant	Background value for empty cells in grid-based pooling.	0
pool_dim	Output dimension of the interaction vector.	256
sample	Sample ratio when loading train/val scenes.	1.0

TABLE 4.11: Relevant training hyperparameters and their values (default values were used).

3. Training a model with the partial dataset

A preliminary training experiment was conducted using only a subset of the dataset files: `biwi_hotel`, `biwi_eth`, `crowds_students001`, `crowds_students003`, `crowds_zara01`, `crowds_zara03` and `lcas`.

This subset represents less than 2 % of the full dataset, containing 9,519 scenes compared to the 496,206 scenes in the complete dataset (see Table A.1 in the Appendix A). The purpose of using this small subset was not for evaluation, but rather to minimise the training time, become familiar with the code and facilitate debugging.

To train the model, the use of a GPU was decided. Since no suitable GPU was available on local hardware, it was necessary to explore companies providing GPUs on demand. These services are becoming increasingly popular due to the rapid growth of AI applications. Among the available options, RunPod [127] was identified as a suitable choice: it offers low-cost instances (starting from only a few cents per hour), requires no prior authorization to begin, follows a pay-as-you-go model, and provides a wide range of GPU types. In addition, RunPod provides free technical support, including direct contact with engineers and the possibility of video calls. This feature was particularly valuable given the limited prior experience with cloud-based GPU services.

To select a suitable GPU model for any AI computing task, the following technical features are the most important to consider:

- **VRAM (Video RAM):** It is the dedicated memory on the GPU. It is used to store data during computation, including model parameters, input batches and intermediate activations. Larger VRAM allows handling bigger models, larger datasets and higher batch sizes without memory overflow errors. Insufficient VRAM can severely limit the ability to work with complex models or high-volume data.
- **RAM (Random Access Memory):** The main memory of the machine, used for temporarily storing data and instructions that the CPU needs while programs are running. RAM supports data preprocessing, loading and efficiently feeding data to the GPU. Larger RAM allows handling bigger datasets and more complex pipelines without slowdowns. Insufficient RAM can create bottlenecks, causing data-loading delays or even training crashes.
- **vCPU (Virtual Central Processing Unit):** A virtualised portion of a physical CPU allocated to the machine. vCPUs handle tasks not performed on the GPU, such as data preprocessing, input/output operations and orchestrating training jobs. More vCPUs allow faster data handling, reduced GPU idle time, and better overall training throughput. Insufficient vCPUs can create bottlenecks, slowing down training and underutilising the GPU.

Initially, the wide range of available GPUs (see Table 4.12) made it unclear which option to select. The strategy was to begin with the most inexpensive instance, set up the environment, train the model for a single epoch, and measure the required time. Based on this result, the total training cost for 25 epochs could then be estimated and assessed for affordability.

From the available catalogue, only GPUs in the “Secure Cloud”⁶ were considered. According to the RunPod GPU catalogue shown in Table 4.12, the most inexpensive option is the RTX 2000 Ada (\$0.24/h), followed by the RTX A4500 and the RTX A4000 (both at \$0.25/h). Comparing their specifications, the RTX A4500 offers the best price-to-performance ratio: it costs the same as the RTX A4000, which has lower technical specifications (VRAM, RAM, and vCPUs), and only \$0.01/h more than the RTX 2000 Ada, while providing 8 GB of additional VRAM (a 50 % increase), 15 GB more RAM (a 200 % increase), and 6 extra vCPUs (a 200 % increase). For these reasons, the RTX A4500 was selected.

Category	Model	VRAM (GB)	RAM (GB)	vCPU	Price (\$/h)
Recommended GPUs	B200	180	180	28	5.99
	H200 SXM	141	168	12	3.79
	A40	48	48	9	0.4
	RTX 5090	32	46	8	0.89
NVIDIA Latest Gen	RTX PRO 6000	96	282	16	1.96
	H100 NVL	94	94	16	2.79
	H100 SXM	80	125	20	2.69
	H100 PCIe	80	176	16	2.39
	L40	48	250	16	0.89
	L40S	48	62	8	0.86
	RTX 6000 Ada	48	80	12	0.77
	RTX 4090	24	36	8	0.69
	L4	24	19	4	0.39
	RTX 4000 Ada	20	47	12	0.26
RTX 2000 Ada	16	15	5	0.24	
NVIDIA Previous Gen	A100 PCIe	80	117	16	1.64
	A100 SXM	80	117	16	1.74
	RTX A6000	48	50	8	0.49
	RTX 3090	24	124	16	0.46
	RTX A5000	24	25	10	0.27

⁶In RunPod, the “Secure Cloud” provides dedicated and vetted infrastructure, ensuring consistent performance, redundancy and compliance with security standards. In contrast, the “Community Cloud” offers a more cost-effective and decentralised option, but its performance and availability can vary depending on individual providers, making it less suitable for experiments requiring reproducibility and stability.

Table 4.12 continued from previous page

Category	Model	VRAM (GB)	RAM (GB)	vCPU	Price (\$/h)
	RTX A4500	24	30	10	0.25
	RTX A4000	16	28	5	0.25
AMD	MI300X	192	283	24	2.69

TABLE 4.12: RunPod GPU catalogue showing the available models in the “Secure Cloud”, categorised by generation/vendor, with hardware specifications (VRAM, RAM, vCPU) and hourly pricing.

RunPod provides GPU access via an SSH connection, which allowed us to connect to the machine and easily set up the project by pulling the GitHub repository created for this work [128].

Once the environment and all necessary dependencies were set up, training was initiated using the following command:

```
$ python -m trajnetbaselines.lstm.trainer \
  --path synth_data \
  --type "social" \
  --seed 42 \
  --disable-cuda
```

The first epoch of the training process required approximately 20 minutes to complete. Based on this initial observation, the total training time for 25 epochs was preliminarily estimated as

$$25 \text{ epochs} \times 20 \text{ minutes/epoch} = 500 \text{ minutes} \approx 8.33 \text{ hours.}$$

Given the computational cost of \$0.25 per hour, the predicted total cost for completing the training was calculated as

$$8.33 \text{ h} \times 0.25 \text{ \$/h} \approx \$ 2.08.$$

Both the estimated duration and cost were considered acceptable for the scope of this preliminary experiment.

Upon completion of the training, the initial estimation was verified using the training log. From the log file, a plot of the training time per epoch was generated (see Fig. 4.24). The results indicated that the duration of each epoch was highly consistent, with a mean of 19.55 minutes and a standard deviation of 0.04 minutes.

Extrapolating this more precise measurement to the full 25 epochs yields a total estimated training time of

$$19.55 \text{ min/epoch} \times 25 \text{ epochs} = 488.75 \text{ minutes} \approx 8.15 \text{ hours,}$$

which is in close agreement with the initial estimate of approximately 8.33 hours.

FIGURE 4.24: Training time per epoch during the preliminary training experiment.

4. Training the model with the full dataset

The preliminary training with the partial dataset, representing less than 2 % of the full dataset, required approximately 8.15 hours. In general, in machine learning, the training time per epoch is expected to increase roughly linearly with the dataset size. Assuming this linear scaling, training on the full dataset would require approximately $8.15/0.02 \approx 407.5$ hours, corresponding to roughly 17 days. This duration is infeasible given the project's time constraints.

For this reason, it was not possible to use the same GPU model as in the preliminary experiments. Instead, the opposite approach was adopted by selecting the most expensive and highest-performing GPU available, with the expectation of minimising training time. The strategy involved training the model for a single epoch on this GPU, recording the epoch duration, and profiling GPU utilization and VRAM usage to refine the hardware requirements. Based on these results, the total cost of running 25 epochs was then estimated to assess feasibility. Consequently, the H200 GPU from Table 4.12 was selected.

After completing the training of the first epoch on this new GPU, it became evident that full training would be infeasible. Despite choosing the most advanced GPU available, equipped with high-end specifications (128 GB VRAM, 180 GB RAM and 28 vCPU), the first epoch required nearly 8 hours to complete. This implied that completing 25 epochs would take approximately 200 hours, making the cost of training infeasible due to the budget and also time:

$$200 \text{ h} \times 5.99 \text{ \$/h} = \$1,198.$$

Both the expected training time 200 hours (8.33 days) and the cost \$1,198 were not acceptable.

At this stage of the project, work was being carried out within the research group of Prof. Emilio Frazzoli at the university of the ETH Zurich in the Institute for Dynamic Systems and Control (IDSC) [129]. Through this collaboration, access to the group's GPU cluster was available. This resource was therefore considered for the training, and permission to use it was subsequently granted.

The technical specifications of the IDSC GPU cluster are as follows:

- RAM: 256 GB
- vCPUs: 40
- VRAM: 12 GB/GPU
- Total number of available GPUs: 7

Training the model using multiple GPUs had not been considered initially, as the aim was to use the original training code provided in the `trajnetplusplusbaselines` repository [92], which was designed for a single GPU.

However, given the opportunity to use IDSC GPU cluster with no cost, the code was modified to enable parallel training across 7 GPUs, thereby significantly reducing the training time. After evaluating several approaches, `DistributedDataParallel` (DDP) [130] was identified as the most suitable solution for this purpose.

DDP allows training the same model simultaneously on multiple GPUs. Each GPU keeps its own copy of the model, and after each backward pass, DDP automatically synchronises the gradients between all GPUs so that every model copy is updated consistently. In practice, this means that before starting a new epoch, all GPUs wait until the others have finished their computations, ensuring synchronization. Each GPU runs its own process, and each process is assigned a unique identifier called a *rank*, with rank 0 designated as the main process responsible for tasks such as saving the model to a `.pk1` file, thereby avoiding conflicts during parallel training.

To ensure that each rank has the same number of training steps, the dataset was first trimmed to a multiple of the total batch size across all ranks and then manually sharded, so that each rank processes a distinct portion of the data. Before each epoch, the training data was deterministically shuffled in the same way across all ranks, ensuring consistency in the data distribution. During training, all processes perform forward and backward passes on their respective data shards, and gradient synchronization ensures that every model copy is updated consistently across ranks.

Once the training code was modified to support multi-GPU training using DDP, it was tested on the cluster by launching these commands:

```
$ set -x CUDA_VISIBLE_DEVICES 1,2,3,4,5,6,7

$ env OMP_NUM_THREADS=(math --scale 0 (nproc) / 7) \
time torchrun --nproc_per_node=7 \
-m trajnetbaselines.lstm.trainer_multi_gpu_fixed \
--path trajdata \
--type social \
--seed 42 \
--distributed \
--ddp-find-unused
```

As explained previously, instead of a single GPU processing the entire dataset, DDP distributes the data evenly across the available GPUs. With this modification, the first epoch was completed in approximately 4.75 hours. Based on this, the estimated total training time for 25 epochs was reduced to roughly 118.75 hours, equivalent to about 5 days. Given that other parts of the project could be advanced concurrently and no direct cost was incurred for using the GPU cluster, this training time was considered acceptable.

However, a new change was introduced to prevent unnecessary computation and save time. Specifically, the training process was now monitored using both the training and validation losses. When the validation loss stops decreasing, it indicates that the model has reached its optimal generalization, and further training is unlikely to improve performance on unseen data. To address this, early stopping [131] was applied with a patience of 3 epochs, meaning that training was terminated if the validation loss did not improve for 2 consecutive epochs. The final model was then selected from the checkpoints corresponding to the lowest validation loss.

It is worth noting that the training time could be affected by concurrent use of the cluster by other researchers, as access was not exclusive. Nevertheless, access to the GPU cluster represented a unique opportunity. Performing this training in the cloud was estimated to require approximately 8.33 days and cost around \$1,200. Independently constructing a comparable cluster with 7 GPUs would have required an investment exceeding at least \$5,000⁷, which was not feasible with the available resources. ETH Zurich is therefore gratefully acknowledged for providing access to this high-performance infrastructure.

Fig. 4.25 shows the training and validation loss over the epochs. Training loss decreases continuously over time, following an approximately linear trajectory with decreasing slopes: a sharp initial reduction (epochs 0–2), a moderate decrease (2–10), another sharp reduction (10–11) and a soft decrease thereafter (11–17). This progression indicates a decrease in optimisation gains as the model approaches flatter regions of the loss landscape.

On the other hand, validation loss decreases rapidly in the early epochs, shows slight oscillations with further improvement around epochs 10–11, and then stabilises. The minimum is reached at approximately epoch 11; beyond this point, training loss continues to decrease, while validation loss remains practically unchanged, indicating the onset of overfitting [133]. Overfitting occurs when validation loss not only stops improving but also diverges from the training loss, whereas ideally both curves should continue decreasing in a similar fashion, reflecting good generalisation to unseen data. In this case, however, such divergence is not observed, so the model maintains good generalisation capability.

The sharp drop in both training loss and validation loss is probably due to a change in the learning rate. From the outset, the learning rate was programmed—rather than fixed—to facilitate convergence, using a gradual decrease policy that reduces the rate by a factor of 10 every 10 epochs (see Fig. 4.26). This decrease explains the notable improvement around this epoch; thereafter, progress in both losses becomes more gradual as parameter updates proceed in smaller steps.

The validation loss appears to plateau from epoch 11 onward. However, a small but consistent decrease persists—though not easily discernible at the plot’s scale—

⁷This amount was calculated by multiplying the number of GPUs (7) by the price of a single GPU (\$ 795, according to Newegg [132], a major American online retailer of electronic products).

FIGURE 4.25: Training and validation loss over epoch.

with the minimum reached exactly at epoch 14. According to the early-stopping criterion (patience = 3), training halts after three consecutive epochs without validation improvement.

Finally, the checkpoint at epoch 15 was selected as the nearest persisted model (.pkl file) to the validation minimum (epoch 14), given the checkpointing interval (save_every = 5).

Evaluation

Evaluation was conducted using the model checkpoint saved at epoch 15 (lstm_social_None.pkl.epoch15). The evaluation was executed with the following command:

```
$ time python -m trajnetbaselines.lstm.trajnet_evaluator \
  --path trajdata \
  --output /home/crodrigue/catkin_ws/src/traj_pred/scripts/ \
  /trajnetplusplusbaselines/OUTPUT_BLOCK_MULTI_GPU/ \
  /trajdata/lstm_social_None.pkl.epoch15 \
  --model_name lstm_social_None_epoch15
```

After running the code, a folder named `test_pred` was generated, containing .ndjson files with the predicted pedestrian trajectories for each scene. To visualise the results, Fig. 4.27 shows a 2D trajectory plot of an example scene from the `biwi_hotel` dataset, comparing the predicted trajectory (blue solid line) with the ground-truth trajectory (black solid line) of the primary pedestrian.

FIGURE 4.26: Learning rate over epoch.

Additionally, a `.png` image was created showing the resulting evaluation metrics described in the baseline paper [93], which quantify the quality of the predictions by comparing the predicted trajectories with the ground-truth ones, contained in the `test_private` folder.

The performance metrics are explained below:

1. **ADE (Average Displacement Error):** Mean Euclidean (L2) distance computed between the predicted and ground-truth positions of the primary pedestrian over all predicted time steps. The lower its value, the better.
2. **FDE (Final Displacement Error):** Euclidean (L2) distance between the predicted final position and the ground-truth final position of the primary pedestrian at the end of the prediction horizon. The lower its value, the better.
3. **Col I (prediction collision):** Proportion of primary-pedestrian trajectories that collide with any neighbouring pedestrian in the *predicted future* scene. The lower its value, the better.
4. **Col II (ground-truth collision):** Proportion of primary-pedestrian trajectories that collide with any neighbouring pedestrian in the *ground-truth future* scene. The lower its value, the better.

Table 4.13 reports the evaluation metrics on the test set, while Table 4.14 reports the same metrics for the test set, categorised by scene type.

Scenes no.	ADE (m)	FDE (m)	Col I (%)	Coll II (%)
134587	0.71	1.39	27.75	31.71

TABLE 4.13: Summary of the evaluation metrics (ADE, FDE, Coll I, and Coll II) computed on the test set.

FIGURE 4.27: 2D trajectory plot showing the comparison between the predicted and ground truth trajectory of the primary pedestrian in an example scene.

Type	Scenes no.	ADE (m)	FDE (m)	Col I (%)	Col II (%)
I	357	0.71	1.52	13.45	15.97
II	35260	0.10	0.22	27.10	29.15
III	90939	0.93	1.80	29.93	34.85
III: LF	31068	0.79	1.53	31.78	37.59
III: CA	53635	0.94	1.82	34.76	39.34
III: Grp	2515	0.58	1.18	27.36	35.86
III: Oth	25112	0.98	1.94	22.85	27.81
IV	8031	0.88	1.84	6.45	8.08

TABLE 4.14: Evaluation metrics (ADE, FDE, Coll I, and Coll II) on the test set, categorised by scene type.

For collision avoidance, per-step accuracy matters more than the final-step error, because the local planner reoptimises the trajectory at a user-defined periodicity. Therefore, ADE is the more informative metric than FDE.

On the full test set, $\text{ADE} = 0.71$ m and $\text{FDE} = 1.39$ m; for type III scenes, these values are slightly higher ($\text{ADE} = 0.93$ m, $\text{FDE} = 1.80$ m).

These values describe the uncertainty with which a person’s position can be predicted. Visually, this can be represented as a “do-not-enter” circle around the predicted point; the robot should stay outside this circle to avoid potential collisions. In practice, the larger the ADE, the larger the safety margin that should be enforced.

To set this safety margin, a simple approach is to set it to three times the ADE, that is,

$$3 \times \text{ADE} = 3 \times 0.71 = 2.13 \text{ m.}$$

This provides a conservative buffer that accounts for most of the pedestrian position uncertainty, reducing the risk of collisions.

Real-time inference

Once the evaluation finished, it became necessary to extend the existing code to enable real-time inference. This was because the current code could only make predictions using the evaluation function, which takes as model input the data read from the `.ndjson` files contained in the `test_private` and `test` folders, but it cannot perform real-time predictions.

For this purpose, a new Python class named `RealTimePredictor` was created. Its main responsibilities include:

1. Loading the trained model by providing the path to the `.pkl` file.
2. Receiving a matrix containing the `obs_length` positions of the pedestrians in the scene and predicting their future trajectories, outputting an array of length `pred_length` for each pedestrian.
3. Optionally visualising the observed and predicted pedestrian trajectories in real time.

As explained in the implementation, the main script in the `traj_pred` node subscribes to the topic `/people_tracked` to receive the 2D poses of all pedestrians detected and tracked in the scene. These messages are received at a frequency of 10 Hz.

However, to match the sampling frequency of the pedestrian trajectory dataset, which is 2.5 Hz, the callback was modified to discard any message unless at least 0.4 s had passed since the previous processed message. Any intermediate messages are ignored.

The main script (the file `traj_pred_code.py` contained in the project directory `catkin_ws/src/traj_pred/scripts/` [128]) constructs the trajectory of each pedestrian and stores it in a custom data structure called `SceneData`. This structure implements a collection of FIFOs (first-in, first-out) queues, one for each pedestrian, where new observations are appended to the end and the oldest samples are automatically removed once the capacity is reached. If no tracking data is available for a pedestrian at a given time step, a NaN (Not a Number) sample of is appended. The pedestrian’s FIFO queue is removed from the structure only when all observations for that pedestrian are NaN values. This design allows the system to efficiently maintain a sliding window of each pedestrian’s most recent trajectory.

At each time step, the system checks whether at least one valid observation exists for any pedestrian in each frame. If so, the mentioned data structure is passed to the `predict` function of the `RealTimePredictor` class, once for each pedestrian in the scene. This is necessary because the Social LSTM method guarantees a reliable prediction only for the first pedestrian in the scene (the primary pedestrian), as explained previously in the implementation section. To address this, the order of

the matrix containing each pedestrian queue is reordered so that each pedestrian is treated as the primary one in turn.

Each prediction array obtained in the loop is stored in a Python dictionary, where the pedestrian ID serves as the key and the corresponding predicted trajectory as the value. Once all predicted trajectories are collected, the script publishes this dictionary in the appropriate format to the `/people_predicted_positions` topic. It also publishes markers for visualization and debugging in RViz, and plots the pedestrian trajectories in real-time updating a Matplotlib [134] figure if specified.

It is important to note that the pedestrian ID used in tracking is conserved and remains the same during prediction, ensuring that each predicted trajectory can be correctly associated with the corresponding pedestrian over time.

To individually run this node in simulation after compiling the project and sourcing the setup file—and assuming the previous `leg_tracker` and `leg_tracker_sim` nodes are running—the following command is used:

```
$ rosrun traj_pred traj_pred_code.py --model_path <model_path>
```

The additional argument `--no_plot` can be added to avoid generating a real-time plot of the predicted trajectories, which is useful for speeding up the simulation.

Below is an example message published to the topic `/people_predicted_positions`. This is timestamped and contains an array of the predicted pedestrian trajectories at that moment:

```

$ rostopic echo /people_predicted_positions
header:
  seq: 1
  stamp:
    secs: 21
    nsecs: 867000000
  frame_id: "map"
agent_trajectories:
-
  id: 10
  poses:
  -
    position:
      x: 3.064425230026245
      y: 0.2729673981666565
      z: 0.0
    orientation:
      x: 0.0
      y: 0.0
      z: 0.0
      w: 1.0
  -
    position:
      x: 2.111032724380493
      y: 0.2951819896697998
      z: 0.0
    orientation:
      x: 0.0
      y: 0.0
      z: 0.0
      w: 1.0
  -
    ...
  ---
  ...

```

Several tests were conducted to measure the inference time, that is, the delay introduced by the `predict` function of the `RealTimePredictor` class when called. The results show that this delay is negligible for real-time applications, as all measured inference times were below 0.1 seconds.

Fig. 4.28 shows an example 2D trajectory of a simulated pedestrian in the scene, following constant-velocity motion. Dots represent the observed (x, y) positions, while crosses represent the predicted (x, y) positions. The trajectory contains 8 crosses, corresponding to the value of the parameter `pred_length`, followed by 6 dots, corresponding to the value of the parameter `obs_length`.

FIGURE 4.28: Example 2D trajectory of a pedestrian moving at constant velocity.

4.3.6 Collision evaluation

The collision evaluation module was fully implemented through the ROS node `coll_eval`. The main script (the file `coll_eval_code.py` contained in the project directory `catkin_ws/src/coll_eval/scripts/` [128]) is responsible for evaluating potential collisions between the robot and the pedestrians in the scene based on their future trajectories.

On the one hand, the main script subscribes to the topic `/people_predicted_positions` to receive the 2D poses corresponding to the predicted trajectories of the pedestrians in the scene.

On the other hand, it subscribes to the topic `/move_base/TebLocalPlanner/local_plan`. When the robot receives a goal, the local planner tries to compute a feasible trajectory that drives the robot toward the goal while respecting its constraints. Here is an example of the message published in this topic, which is composed of a series of poses that represent the discretised points along the planned trajectory. Each pose is expressed in the odometry frame and includes both a position (x, y, z) and an orientation, represented as a quaternion:

```

$ rostopic echo /move_base/TebLocalPlanner/local_plan
...
header:
  seq: 148
  stamp:
    secs: 19
    nsecs: 826000000
  frame_id: "odom"
poses:
-
  header:
    seq: 0
    stamp:
      secs: 19
      nsecs: 826000000
    frame_id: "odom"
  pose:
    position:
      x: 1.496230898439888
      y: 0.1829609189217436
      z: 0.0
    orientation:
      x: 0.0
      y: 0.0
      z: 0.15072123113487854
      w: 0.9885763048370048
-
...

```

To synchronise the callbacks of the subscribers associated with the predicted pedestrian positions and the robot local path, a joint callback was created using ROS message filters:

```

people_sub = message_filters.Subscriber(
    "/people_predicted_positions", AgentTrajectories)

robot_sub = message_filters.Subscriber("/move_base/
    TebLocalPlannerROS/local_plan", Path)

# Synchronise people and robot path messages.
ats = message_filters.ApproximateTimeSynchronizer([people_sub,
    robot_sub], queue_size=10, slop=0.05)
ats.registerCallback(self.synched_callback)

```

`ApproximateTimeSynchronizer` is used to pair the incoming messages from the pedestrians' predicted positions (`people_sub`) and the robot's local plan (`robot_sub`) that arrive nearly simultaneously. The `slop` parameter allows a small tolerance in timestamps (0.050 s in this case), so messages that are close in time but not perfectly

aligned are still considered synchronised. Once a pair of messages is matched, the specified callback function `synched_callback` is invoked to process them together.

To transform the coordinate reference frame from the “odom” frame to the “map” frame, the following function `_get_transform` was implemented:

```
def _get_transform(self, header_frame_id, header_stamp,
                  target_frame="map", timeout=rospy.Duration(0.1)) ->
    Optional[TransformStamped]:
    """
    Get the transform from the robot's frame to the map frame.

    Args:
        header_frame_id (str): Frame ID of the header.
        header_stamp (rospy.Time): Timestamp of the header.
        target_frame (str): Target frame.
        timeout (rospy.Duration): Timeout for the transform.

    Returns:
        Optional[geometry_msgs.msg.TransformStamped]: Transform
        from the robot's frame to the map frame.
    """
    try:
        return self.tf_buffer.lookup_transform(
            target_frame,          # target: map
            header_frame_id,      # source: odom
            header_stamp,         # timestamp of original path
            timeout)              # timeout

    except (tf2_ros.LookupException,
            tf2_ros.ConnectivityException,
            tf2_ros.ExtrapolationException):
        rospy.logwarn_throttle(5.0,
            "TF transform from %s to map not available yet",
            header_frame_id)

    return None
```

In the constructor of the Python class `CollisionEvaluator`, the ROS parameter `/move_base/TebLocalPlannerROS/dt_ref` was set to 0.4 to match the sampling rate of the pedestrian trajectory forecasting dataset, which is 2.5 Hz (a sample every 0.4 s):

```
self.target_interval = rospy.get_param("/target_interval",
                                       default=0.4)
rospy.set_param("/move_base/TebLocalPlannerROS/dt_ref",
               self.target_interval)
```

In order to publish the potential collisions to the topic `/potential_collisions`, the custom messages named `PotentialCollision.msg` and `PotentialCollisions.msg` were created. The first defines the structure of a single collision instance and

consists of the fields `id` (collision ID), `ttc` (time to collision) and `dtc` (distance to collision).

```
# Potential collision
uint32 id
geometry_msgs/Point poc
float32 ttc          # seconds
float32 dtc          # meters
```

The second message, `PotentialCollisions.msg`, is used to group multiple potential collision instances within a single message. Its structure is defined as follows:

```
# Potential collisions
std_msgs/Header header
PotentialCollision[] collisions
```

The logic for comparing the robot path with the future trajectory of each pedestrian is contained in the `compare_with_robot_path` function. The routine can be summarised in the following steps:

1. **Initialise the transformed robot path:** Create an empty list named `transformed_robot_path` to store the robot's poses transformed into the map frame.
2. **Trim the robot path:** Remove the first pose (current robot position) and limit the path to `self.pred_length` steps.
3. **Get the transform:** Retrieve the transformation from the robot's frame to the map frame using the function `_get_transform`.
4. **Transform robot poses:** Apply the transform to each pose in the trimmed robot path and append the results to the list `transformed_robot_path`.
5. **Pad with NaNs if needed:** Ensure that the list `transformed_robot_path` has exactly `self.pred_length` poses by appending poses with NaN coordinates if necessary.
6. **Initialise the potential collisions message:** Create a `PotentialCollisions` message with the current timestamp and map frame.
7. **Iterate over predicted pedestrian trajectories:** For each person ID and their predicted trajectory:
 - (a) Iterate through each predicted position and the corresponding transformed robot pose.
 - (b) Skip any robot positions containing NaN values.
8. **Compute distance to collision (DTC):** Calculate the Euclidean distance between the robot and the pedestrian predicted positions at each time step.
9. **Check for potential collisions:** If the DTC is below the safety distance:
 - (a) Log the collision details (robot position, pedestrian position, DTC, TTC).
 - (b) Create a `PotentialCollision` message and append it to the `collisions` array.

10. **Return all potential collisions:** After iterating through all pedestrians, return the `PotentialCollisions` message containing all the detected potential collisions which will be published immediately afterwards.

To individually run this node in simulation after compiling the project and sourcing the setup file—and assuming the previous `leg_tracker`, `leg_tracker_sim` and `traj_pred` nodes are running—the following command is used:

```
$ rosruncoll_eval coll_eval_code.py
```

Below is an example message published to the topic `/potential_collisions`. This is timestamped and contains an array of the potential collisions detected at that moment:

```
$ rostopic echo /potential_collisions
header:
  seq: 1
  stamp:
    secs: 21
    nsecs: 0
  frame_id: "map"
collisions:
-
  id: 0
  poc:
    x: 2.4866056757116914
    y: 0.4502871675772172
    z: 0.0
  ttc: 0.4000000059604645
  dtc: 1.309999942779541
-
...
---
```

4.3.7 Collision avoidance

The collision avoidance module was fully implemented through the ROS node `coll_avoid`. The main script, `coll_avoid_code.py`, located in the project directory `catkin_ws/src/coll_avoid/scripts/` [128], subscribes to the topic `/potential_collisions` to receive the predicted collisions between the robot and the pedestrians in the scene. It publishes them as obstacles to the topic `/move_base/TebLocalPlannerROS/obstacles`, enabling the local planner to replan and avoid collisions.

The logic for publishing the obstacles for the local planner is inside the `potential_collisions_callback` function. The routine can be summarised in the following steps:

1. **Check collision avoidance status:** If the collision avoidance module is disabled, log a message and exit the callback without processing. This option is provided to enable evaluation of the baseline configuration.
2. **Initialise the obstacle message:** Create an empty `ObstacleArrayMsg` message with the current timestamp and selecting "map" as the frame ID.
3. **Initialise the visualization markers:** Create an empty `MarkerArray` message for visualization in RViz, using the current timestamp.
4. **Iterate over potential collisions:** For each `PotentialCollisions` message received in the `/potential_collisions` topic:
 - (a) **Create an obstacle:**
 - Initialise an `ObstacleMsg` message.
 - Set its position to the point of collision.
 - Assign a predefined radius, ID (incremental ID) and default orientation.
 - Append it to the obstacles array.
 - (b) **Create a marker:**
 - Initialise a cylindrical `Marker` message.
 - Set its namespace, ID (incremental ID), position and default orientation, and size based on the specified radius.
 - Define its colour (semi-transparent red) and lifetime (0.5 seconds).
 - Append it to the marker array.
5. **Publish the results:** Publish the populated `ObstacleArrayMsg` and `MarkerArray` messages.

To individually run this node in simulation after compiling the project and sourcing the setup file —and assuming the previous `leg_tracker`, `leg_tracker_sim`, `traj_pred` and `coll_eval` nodes are running— the following command is used:

```
$ rosrn coll_avoid coll_avoid_code.py
```

Below is an example message published in the topic `/move_base/TebLocalPlannerROS/obstacles`. This is timestamped and contains an array of the obstacles at that moment:

```

$ rostopic echo /move_base/TebLocalPlannerROS/obstacles
header:
  seq: 1
  stamp:
    secs: 24
    nsecs: 904000000
  frame_id: "map"
obstacles:
-
  header:
    seq: 0
    stamp:
      secs: 0
      nsecs: 0
    frame_id: ""
  polygon:
    points:
      -
        x: 2.8878448009490967
        y: 0.8221568465232849
        z: 0.0
    radius: 0.25
    id: 1
    orientation:
      x: 0.0
      y: 0.0
      z: 0.0
      w: 1.0
    velocities:
      twist:
        linear:
          x: 0.0
          y: 0.0
          z: 0.0
        angular:
          x: 0.0
          y: 0.0
          z: 0.0
    covariance: [0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0,
0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0,
0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0,
0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0]
-
  ...
  ...

```

Fig. 4.29 is a screenshot of an RViz window showing an example collision detection when simulating the scenario “SA-S1”:

FIGURE 4.29: Visualization in RViz of an example collision detection when simulating the scenario “SA-S1”.

4.4 System real-world deployment

4.4.1 Open-source release and reproducibility

The project was publicly released online to promote reproducibility and to enable other researchers and developers to easily replicate, test and extend the system. The aim is that this project serves as a baseline that allows researchers to focus on developing their algorithms rather than dealing with the underlying infrastructure, thanks to a quick and straightforward simulation setup.

The following resources have been made publicly available:

- The code implementation of our PCA system was developed as a dedicated ROS package and is publicly available in this repository [128], hosted on GitHub [105]. Setup instructions are provided in the `README.md` file of the same repository.
- A Docker container was published on Docker Hub [123]. This container includes the required operating system, a graphical user interface (GUI) accessible via VNC (KasmVNC [135]), the complete source code and simulation environment, and all necessary dependencies —providing a ready-to-use setup for running the system without any additional configuration.

As a result, and thanks to its compatibility with ROS, this work is expected to be adapted not only for TIAGo but also for other robotic platforms used in daily life, such as four-wheeled robots designed for delivery in urban environments.

Beyond research and development purposes, this work is also intended to benefit the educational community. Setting up a ROS environment and simulation setup typically requires multiple steps, which might involve creating disk partitions, installing Ubuntu, configuring dependencies and other related tasks. Of course, this can discourage newcomers from engaging with the framework. By providing a Docker-based

solution, these barriers can be reduced, offering educators an accessible tool for teaching. Since Docker runs on multiple platforms (macOS, Windows, Linux), the setup is straightforward and cross-platform, making it easier for students and instructors alike.

4.4.2 Deployment considerations in the TIAGo robot

For this work, as specified earlier (Section 4.1.2), the version of the robot TIAGo used was the one available at the university (TIAGo (standard version) [73]), which includes a single arm, a differential drive base, a parallel gripper and a laser range finder. This setup is the basic one and it does not include all the features of more advanced configurations.

The name of TIAGo's computer follows the format `tiago-<serial_number>c`, where `<serial_number>` must be replaced with the actual serial number of the robot. This system runs on Ubuntu 20.04 with ROS Noetic as the middleware. It operates by creating a wireless access point to which the development computer must connect.

The access point uses the SSID `PAL-Robotics`, password `P@L-R0b0t1cs` and the IP network address `10.68.0.0/24`, enabling communication between the robot and the development computer. The robot is assigned the IP address `10.68.0.1`, while the development computer is typically assigned the first IP address in the range from `10.68.0.128` to `10.68.0.254`.

Access point default configuration

SSID	PAL-Robotics
Channel	1
Mode key	WPA-PSK
Password	P@L-R0b0t1cs
Robot IP	10.68.0.1

FIGURE 4.30: TIAGo access point configuration. [75]

A secure connection to the robot can be established from the development computer via SSH by executing the following command in the terminal: `ssh pal@tiago-<serial_number>c`. Thanks to this connection, it is possible to remotely access the robot's internal files, execute commands, and monitor its status as if working directly on the robot itself. However, to execute the code of this project [128], this is not necessary.

The only prerequisites for executing the code are determining the robot's serial number, required for the environment variable `ROS_MASTER_URI`, and ensuring that the computer is connected to the robot's network with its IP address known within that network (`ROS_IP`). Once these conditions are met, the following commands can be executed, substituting the appropriate values as needed. The example below assumes `ROS_IP=10.68.0.128` and a robot with serial number 0:

```
$ export ROS_MASTER_URI=http://tiago-0c:11311
$ export ROS_IP=10.68.0.128
```

The diagram below illustrates a graphical representation of the resulting network setup:

FIGURE 4.31: Graphical representation of the network setup.

(a) SSH connection between the development computer and the robot.

(b) Physical drawing. (c) Logic drawing.

To encapsulate both the required prerequisites and the complete launch procedure of the project code, a dedicated Bash script named `launch_deploy.sh` was created. With this script, the full pipeline can be started on the robot with a single command:

```
$ chmod +x launch_deploy.sh # Give permission to execute the file.
$ ./launch_deploy.sh        # Run the script to start the project.
```

One good recommendation is to periodically check the “Web Commander” [75]. This is a tool provided by the company’s robot PAL Robotics that enables users to monitor, configure, and control their robot remotely through a web interface. It is very useful for diagnostics, as it helps detect errors that could leave the robot stuck and unable to start the most simple routines.

Chapter 5

Evaluation of the Predictive Avoidance Collision (PCA) system

This chapter provides the evaluation of the PCA system in comparison to the baseline system. First, it describes the preparation of the simulation task and then it illustrates the process of performing the designed task.

5.1 Preparation of the simulation task

5.1.1 Creating a map of the scenario

In the definition of the simulation task (see Section 4.1.4), it was established that the robot may or may not have access to a prior map. As it is necessary to simulate the scenarios numerous times, it is more convenient to assume that the robot has previously traversed this area and possesses a map of the environment. This is because, when provided with a goal, the robot can navigate more effectively, as the map enables it to self-localise. Even though the robot employs SLAM to simultaneously map the environment and localise itself, possessing a pre-existing map significantly reduces uncertainty and computational effort. In this case, SLAM primarily serves for localisation against the known map rather than for continuous reconstruction of the environment, which not only accelerates the simulation but also ensures greater consistency between trials.

The map of the environment was created by following the tutorial in [136]. It is available in the GitHub repository in the directory `catkin_ws/navigation_files/car_1_junction_v5`. Fig. 5.1 shows a bird's-eye view of the resulting map in RViz.

This map provides a partial representation of the environment, as the region of interest is centred on the intersection between the two main streets of the Gazebo world. In this occupancy grid, black areas correspond to walls or occupied cells, white areas indicate free space, and grey areas denote regions with unknown data. Superimposed on this occupancy grid, black circular patches can be observed. These patches represent the endpoints of the laser scans projected into the map frame according to the current set of pose hypotheses maintained by the robot's localization system (AMCL [137]). Initially, when the particles are widely scattered across the environment, these projected points appear distributed throughout the map. As the simulation evolves, the localization process advances: invalid hypotheses are discarded and the black patches gradually align with the occupied regions of the map, ensuring a consistent match between sensor data and the static environment representation.

FIGURE 5.1: Bird's-eye view of the map of the simulated world in RViz.

5.1.2 Creating the global ROS node `tfg_launch`

The ROS node named `tfg_launch` was created to simplify the execution of the nodes contained in the `catkin_ws/src` directory (`leg_tracker`, `leg_tracker_sim`, `traj_pred`, etc.). This node contains a file named `launch/tfg_sim.launch`, which automatically initialises them together ensuring that all the dependencies are properly started in the correct order.

As a result, the node `tfg_launch` acts as a wrapper that aggregates the individual launch files of the system into one unified structure, which can be jointly launched with the following `roslaunch` command, as shown below:

```
$ roslaunch tfg_launch tfg_sim.launch \
  cylinder_model_path:=$CYLINDER_MODEL_PATH \
  traj_pred_model_path:=$TRAJ_PRED_MODEL_PATH \
  agent_cat:=$AGENT_CAT \
  no_plot:=$NO_PLOT \
  cylinders_flag:=$CYLINDERS_FLAG \
  scenario_id:=$SCENARIO_ID
```

The arguments in this command have default values, but the user can override them if desired.

To execute not only the nodes in the `catkin_ws` folder but also the Gazebo simulator with TIAGo, a Bash script named `launch_sim.sh` was created. This script encapsulates the complete launch procedure, enabling the full simulation pipeline to be started with a single command:

```
$ chmod +x launch_sim.sh # Give execution permission to the file.
$ ./launch_sim.sh         # Run the script to start the simulation.
```

More importantly, the `launch_sim.sh` script also provides a help message that lists the available arguments and their descriptions, allowing the user to quickly check which parameters can be configured (e.g., `scenario_id`, `agent_cat`) and adapt the simulation to different experimental setups.

This can be checked by executing the following command:

```
$ ./launch_sim.sh -h
```

5.1.3 Calculating the TTC of each scenario

To assess the performance of each scenario, it was first necessary to determine the Theoretical Time to Collision (TTC), which then allowed the computation of the Available Collision Avoidance Time (ACAT).

For this purpose, the helper node `ttc_estimator` was created. This node estimates the TTC experimentally by detecting collisions based on the real-time positions of the robot and pedestrians, and determining the moment a collision occurs in each scenario—that is, when their positions overlap within a predefined threshold, which corresponds to the previously defined security margin of 3 times the ADE (2.13 m).

As previously explained, the idea is to simulate each scenario without representing the pedestrians as physical objects (`--cylinders_flag = False`), allowing the simulation to run freely in order to measure the time from the start until the moment an actual collision would occur. When such a collision is detected, a ROS warning message is printed on the screen, and the TTC is calculated as the time at which this message appears. Here there is an example of this message:

```
[WARN] [1757495788.839419, 31.756000]: Potential collision
detected between pedestrian 10 and the robot!
```

In this message, the value `1757495788.839419` corresponds to the ROS wall-clock time, while the value `31.756000` indicates the simulation time (in seconds) at which the collision was detected. Therefore, the TTC corresponds to 31.756 s, meaning that in this scenario the robot and the pedestrian would collide approximately 31.8 seconds after the start of the simulation.

Table 5.1 shows the topic to which the `ttc_estimator` node subscribes.

ROS node	Subscribed topics
<code>ttc_estimator</code>	<code>/people_positions</code> (PersonArray)
	<code>/move_base/TebLocalPlanner/local_plan</code> (nav_msgs/Path [99])

TABLE 5.1: ROS node interfaces of the TTC estimator module.

5.1.4 Detecting a potential collision in the baseline and PCA configurations

To assess the Collision Detection Time (CDT), it was necessary to determine when the both the baseline system and the PCA system had reacted to that collision.

For the PCA system, the following ROS warning message is printed on the screen by the `coll_eval` module, and the CDT is calculated as the time at which this message appears:

```
[WARN] [1757495788.839419, 31.756000]: Potential collision
detected between person 10 and robot at step 5!
```

In contrast, for the baseline system, this information cannot be inferred directly and requires a more complex determination. For this purpose, the helper node `cm_coll_detect` was created.

The main script subscribes to the topic `/move_base/local_costmap/costmap` to monitor updates to the local costmap, which represents the robot's immediate surroundings and is used by the local planner to compute the local path. Each message received consists of an occupancy grid, where each cell in the local map contains a specific value. According to the documentation provided in [138], each value represents:

- **0:** Free space.
- **1–252:** Inflated obstacle (areas near obstacles, inflated for safety).
- **253:** Inscribed inflated obstacle (core obstacle region).
- **254:** Lethal obstacle (definitely occupied, collision likely).
- **255 or -1:** Unknown (cell has not been observed or is uncertain).

In this case, because the scenario is controlled, any changes in the map can be directly linked to the pedestrians moving around the robot. By logging a timestamped warning whenever a cell is marked as an obstacle, it is possible to identify when the local planner starts reacting to a potential collision and replanning the path. This moment, known as the CDT, can be captured by focusing on cell values in the range 1–252, which represent inflated obstacles. These values appear as soon as a pedestrian enters the robot's costmap, providing an early indication before the obstacle is classified as inscribed or lethal.

Here there is an example of the warning message that appears:

```
[WARN] [1757495390.338783, 27.481000]:
  ▲ Inflated obstacles detected: 7584
```

Table 5.1 lists the subscribed topics of the `cm_coll_detect` node:

ROS node	Subscribed topics
<code>cm_coll_detect</code>	<code>/move_base/local_costmap/costmap</code> (OccupancyGrid [139])

TABLE 5.2: ROS node interfaces of the costmap collision detector module.

5.2 Evaluating the system

During the system evaluation, guided by the procedure explained in Alg. 1, the ROS parameter `/coll_avoid/enabled` was set to `False`. This was done to avoid interfering with the reaction of the system with the baseline configuration.

First, each scenario was executed five times in order to compute the TTC. For this purpose, the `ttc_estimator` node was launched with the parameter `cylinders_flag` set to `False`, so that pedestrians were not represented as physical obstacles in the simulation.

Second, the same set of scenarios was executed five additional times, this time with the `ttc_estimator` node deactivated and the `cm_coll_detect` node launched instead, using `cylinders_flag` set to `True` to enable the representation of pedestrians as physical cylinders. In this configuration, the reaction times of the two systems were determined as follows:

- To detect when the PCA system reacts, the timestamp of the first potential collision message published by the `coll_eval` node was used.
- To detect when the *BL* system reacts, the timestamp of the warning message corresponding to the appearance of an inflated obstacle, published by the `cm_coll_detect` node, was used.

The obtained results are presented in the next chapter (Chapter 6).

Chapter 6

Results

This chapter presents and analyses the experimental results obtained from the simulation task. The evaluation focuses on assessing the performance of the Predictive Collision Avoidance (PCA) system relative to the system with the baseline (BL) configuration.

Table 6.1 summarises the results obtained for the Theoretical Time to Collision (TTC) across all the scenarios. Each interaction type was evaluated in two different scenarios, and each scenario was executed five times to account for variability in the simulations. The table reports the TTC values for each repetition as well as the mean TTC value.

		TTC (s)					
		Rep. no.					Mean
Interact. type	Scen. ID	1	2	3	4	5	
Single-agent	1	29.702	29.506	29.016	29.094	29.386	29.341
	2	46.333	46.816	46.666	45.349	46.419	46.317
Multi-agent	1	27.366	26.931	27.317	27.027	27.735	27.275
	2	45.264	44.495	45.851	44.803	45.989	45.280

TABLE 6.1: TTC results.

Table 6.2 presents the results of the Available Collision Avoidance Time (ACAT) computed for both the PCA and BL configurations across all the scenarios. Again, each interaction type was evaluated using five repetitions per scenario in order to account for variability in the simulations and ensure the robustness of the results. The table reports the individual TTC, CDT and ACAT values for each repetition.

				PCA config		BL config	
Interact. type	Scen. ID	Rep. no.	TTC (s)	DCT (s)	ACAT (s)	DCT (s)	ACAT (s)
	1	1	29.341	25.961	3.380	26.905	2.436
		2		26.641	2.700	27.763	1.578
		3		26.599	2.742	28.597	0.744
		4		26.305	3.036	27.781	1.560
		5		27.074	2.267	28.895	0.446
Single- agent	2	1	46.317	42.249	4.068	42.919	3.398
		2		43.187	3.130	43.776	2.541
		3		42.380	3.937	43.655	2.662
		4		43.693	2.624	44.970	1.347
		5		43.252	3.065	44.168	2.149
	1	1	27.275	26.479	0.796	28.234	-0.959
		2		25.943	1.332	26.920	0.355
		3		25.354	1.921	26.810	0.465
		4		25.322	1.953	26.512	0.763
		5		24.758	2.517	24.917	2.358
Multi- agent	2	1	45.280	43.218	2.062	43.670	1.610
		2		44.199	1.081	44.999	0.281
		3		44.195	1.085	44.605	0.675
		4		44.693	0.587	46.035	-0.755
		5		44.100	0.000	0.000	0.000

TABLE 6.2: ACAT results.

Fig. 6.1 shows a visual comparison of the ACAT values between the PCA and BL configurations in both single-agent and multi-agent interaction scenarios. The boxplots illustrate the distribution of ACAT values across all repetitions: the median is shown as a horizontal line within each box, the interquartile range is represented by the box itself, the whiskers indicate the overall spread of the data, and the dashed white line corresponds to the mean value.

FIGURE 6.1: Comparison of the obtained ACAT values between the PCA and BL system configurations for each interaction type.

The exact mean and standard deviation (std) of the ACAT values for each configuration are reported in Table 6.3. To assess whether the differences in ACAT between the PCA and BL configurations are statistically significant, a paired t-test [140] was conducted. The resulting p -values are included in the table, together with the corresponding improvement factors. For the analysis, all the ACAT values from the SA scenarios were grouped together, as well as those from the MA scenarios. The paired version of the t-test was selected because both configurations (PCA and BL) were evaluated under identical conditions (i.e., same scenarios and repetitions), which allows a direct comparison, thereby reducing variability and increasing the statistical power of the test.

Inter. type	PCA config		BL config		p-value	Improv.
	Mean (s)	Std (s)	Mean (s)	Std (s)		
SA	3.095	0.571	1.886	0.916	< 0.001	64.09 %
MA	1.451	0.625	0.538	0.975	< 0.001	169.93 %
SA \cup MA	2.273	1.025	1.212	1.152	< 0.001	87.57 %

TABLE 6.3: Statistical comparison of the obtained ACAT values between the PCA and BL system configurations.

As shown in Table 6.3, the proposed PCA system consistently achieves higher ACAT values compared to the BL configuration across all the interaction types. This demonstrates that our predictive strategy provides the robot with a larger temporal margin to react before a potential collision.

In the SA cases, the PCA system achieves a mean ACAT of 3.095 s with a standard deviation of 0.571 s, compared to only 1.886 s (std = 0.916 s) for the BL configuration. This corresponds to a relative improvement of 64.09 %.

In the MA scenarios, the PCA system reaches a mean ACAT of 1.451 s (std = 0.625 s), which is considerably higher than the BL result of 0.538 s (std = 0.975 s). The relative improvement here is 169.93 %, which is larger than in the SA scenarios. However, it is important to note that the absolute ACAT mean values in MA cases are lower than in SA, reflecting the increased complexity and reduced temporal margins inherent to MA interactions.

When considering all the scenarios together (SA \cup MA), the PCA system achieves a mean of 2.273 s (std = 1.025 s), compared to 1.212 s (std = 1.152 s) for BL. This yields an overall improvement factor of 87.57 %. This difference is statistically significant (p -value < 0.05), showing that the final improvement obtained when incorporating the PCA configuration to the baseline system is both consistent and robust. In practical terms, this demonstrates that predictive information substantially enhances the robot's ability to anticipate collisions across both SA and MA scenarios, ensuring a safer and more efficient navigation.

Chapter 7

Temporal and Financial Costs

The completion of this project required a careful allocation of both time and financial resources. This chapter provides an overview of the financial and temporal costs. The former details the expenses associated with the different cloud computing tasks required during the project development. The latter is illustrated through a structured schedule that highlights the distribution of activities, their interdependencies, and the overlaps between them.

Together, these analyses provide a comprehensive picture of the resources invested to achieve the final outcomes.

7.1 Financial Costs

Table 7.1 summarises the cloud computing budget during the project development and links each expense to its corresponding task:

Cloud computing task	Cost (\$)
Training the Social-LSTM model with GPU acceleration.	137.61
Running the project with GPU acceleration for Gazebo/Rviz rendering.	25.00
TOTAL	162.61

TABLE 7.1: Cloud computing costs.

7.2 Temporal Costs

A Gantt chart in Fig. 7.1 is provided to present the full set of activities undertaken during the project, along with their planned scheduling, which are described below in Table 7.2:

Phase	Task	Description
1. Analysis	1.1	Research on the topic of the thesis.
	1.2	Reading and analysis of the existing literature.
	1.3	Problem formulation and definition of the research question.

TABLE 7.2: Description of the tasks corresponding to each project phase as illustrated in the Gantt chart.

Phase	Task	Description
	1.4	Theoretical investigation of existing methods.
	1.5	Definition of project objectives.
	1.6	Identification of the technical requirements.
2. Design	2.1	System design at a modular level.
	2.2	Project planning according to requirements.
	2.3	Scheduling of meetings and tutorials.
	2.4	Distribution of tasks in the timeline.
	2.5	Overall architecture and data flow definitions.
	2.6	Selection of supporting tools and technologies.
3. Implementation	3.1	Individual implementation of the system's modules.
	3.2	Integration of the modules into a unified system.
	3.3	Iterative improvements based on partial results.
4. Validation	4.1	Verification of each module separately.
	4.2	Verification of the complete system as a whole.
	4.3	Preparation of the simulation task.
	4.4	Execution of the simulation task.
	4.5	Iterative improvements based on partial results.
5. Documentation	5.1	Drafting the index and Chapter 1.
	5.2	Structuring the content by chapters.
	5.3	Writing and revision of Chapters 2–10.
	5.4	Bibliographic references.
	5.5	Content editing and iterative improvements based on supervision feedback.
	5.6	Preparation of the appendix.
	5.7	Final review.
6. Mentoring	6.1	Bi-weekly follow-up meetings.

TABLE 7.2: Description of the tasks corresponding to each project phase as illustrated in the Gantt chart.

FIGURE 7.1: Gantt chart showing the temporal costs of the project.

Chapter 8

Discussion

The discussion is organised around the six objectives established in Section 1. For each objective, the achieved results, limitations and potential improvements are analysed.

8.1 Objective 1 discussion

Objective 1:

Detect potential collisions with pedestrians through trajectory forecasting.

8.1.1 Results

First, the selected models for human detection, tracking and trajectory prediction were successfully integrated into the navigation stack of a public mobile robot (PMR). Second, the Predictive Collision Avoidance (PCA) system was designed and implemented, enabling the evaluation of potential collisions with a temporal margin before they occur. The implementation was successfully validated and demonstrated. Therefore, this objective can be considered successfully achieved.

8.1.2 Limitations

The performance of the system is significantly constrained by the sampling rate of the dataset used for human trajectory forecasting, which is 2.5 Hz (one sample every 0.4 s). This limits the model's ability to accurately capture and predict the movements of fast-moving pedestrians, since multiple samples are required to establish reliable motion patterns. In addition, the model's training process was computationally expensive, requiring approximately 5 days to complete on the GPU cluster.

Another limitation arises from the sensing capabilities of the robot: the range of the laser scanner restricts pedestrian detection, with earlier detection leading to more reliable predictions.

8.1.3 Suggestions for improvement

Constructing a dataset with a higher sampling frequency (e.g., 10 Hz, corresponding to a 0.1 s interval) would significantly improve the prediction resolution.

To address the high training time, a possible optimization strategy is to upgrade the human trajectory forecasting model to newer library versions (e.g., recent PyTorch releases), explore Automatic Mixed Precision (AMP) [141] to accelerate computations, apply model pruning [142] to reduce model complexity, and extend the current parallelization by distributing training across a larger number of GPUs.

Additionally, extending the sensor range or fusing data from complementary perception modalities (e.g., cameras, depth sensors) could enhance early pedestrian detection and mitigate the limitations imposed by the laser scanner alone.

8.2 Objective 2 discussion

Objective 2:

Achieve real-time execution with low computational cost.

8.2.1 Results

The critical aspect in achieving this objective is the inference time, defined as the delay introduced by the `predict` function of the `RealTimePredictor` Python class when called. On the development computer (the MacBook), the system achieved an inference time of less than 0.1 seconds, which is sufficient to be considered real-time and ensure that the fluidity of navigation was not affected.

However, the overall performance remains constrained by the 2.5 Hz sampling rate of the pedestrian trajectory dataset, meaning that predictions are only updated every 0.4 seconds. Consequently, this objective can be regarded as only partially achieved.

8.2.2 Limitations

The performance of the system is primarily constrained by the 2.5 Hz sampling rate of the pedestrian trajectory dataset, which reduces the ability to capture rapid changes in pedestrian motion and limits the temporal resolution of the predictions. In addition, the system has so far only been evaluated on a single development computer (the MacBook).

8.2.3 Suggestions for improvement

Future work should employ datasets with higher sampling frequencies (e.g., 10 Hz) to improve temporal resolution and responsiveness to fast pedestrian dynamics. This would enable the model to better capture subtle changes in velocity and direction, resulting in more reliable real-time execution.

8.3 Objective 3 discussion

Objective 3:

Validate the system in simulation in a methodological way.

8.3.1 Results

The system was validated in simulation using Gazebo for environment modelling and RViz for visualization. A custom simulation task was designed, covering a diverse range of scenarios in both single-agent and multi-agent interactions. The PCA system was consistently able to detect potential collisions in advance and trigger replanning actions.

Navigation performance was quantitatively assessed using the ACAT (Available Collision Avoidance Time) metric. Qualitative observations were possible thanks to RViz. Consequently, this objective can be considered successfully achieved.

8.3.2 Limitations

Simulated environments are controlled scenarios where many real-world uncertainties are absent, such as sensor noise, imperfect calibration and unexpected human behaviours. As a result, the robot's performance in simulation may not fully reflect its behaviour in the real life (sim-to-real gap).

In addition, the pedestrian physical motion models used in simulation are simplified and may not capture the full variability of human motion, particularly in crowded or unstructured environments.

8.3.3 Suggestions for improvement

Future work should extend validation beyond simulation by conducting experiments in real-world environments or in semi-controlled laboratory settings with human participants, in order to capture sensor noise, imperfect calibration and natural variability in pedestrians' motion. Incorporating more sophisticated pedestrians' motion models in simulation, for example based on real trajectory datasets, would also provide more realistic testing conditions.

Additionally, performing hardware-in-the-loop [143] experiments, where the PCA system runs on the real robot hardware while interacting with a simulated environment, could help to bridge the sim-to-real gap.

8.4 Objective 4 discussion

Objective 4:

Compare the effectiveness of the developed system against the baseline.

8.4.1 Results

The PCA system consistently outperformed the baseline (BL) configuration across all the interaction types. The predictive strategy provided the robot with a larger temporal margin to react to a potential collision both in single-agent and multi-agent scenarios.

Overall, the statistical analysis confirmed that the improvements introduced by PCA were significant and consistent. Consequently, this objective can not only be considered successfully achieved, but it also demonstrates that the PCA system consistently outperforms the BL configuration.

8.4.2 Limitations

A key limitation of the evaluation process is that each experiment must be executed in real time, requiring the full duration of the scenario to be observed before results are obtained. This substantially reduces the number of tests that can be carried out, since data collection is manual and the behaviour of the robot must be visually supervised in RViz.

In addition, prolonged testing leads to overheating issues that can negatively affect the repeatability and reliability of results.

8.4.3 Suggestions for improvement

Automating the data collection and evaluation pipeline would enable larger-scale testing without requiring constant visual supervision in RViz, thereby increasing both the number and diversity of experiments that can be performed.

Moreover, conducting the experiments on more powerful hardware (experiments were carried out with the MacBook), such as dedicated workstations or GPU-equipped servers, would help to mitigate overheating issues and enhance the repeatability of results.

8.5 Objective 5 discussion

Objective 5:

Prepare the system for deployment on a physical robot.

8.5.1 Results

The system was developed with deployment on the TIAGo robot (from PAL Robotics) in mind. The code structure and ROS integration were designed to enable a straightforward deployment. The complete system can be executed through the dedicated Bash script named `launch_deploy.sim`.

However, due to time constraints, full deployment on the physical robot could not be conducted, and only individual components were tested separately. Consequently, this objective can only be considered partially achieved.

8.5.2 Limitations

The main limitation was the time constraint, which prevented a complete validation of the system on the physical TIAGo robot.

In addition, as the sim-to-real gap introduces uncertainty, results obtained in simulation may not fully translate to real-world performance. Therefore, it cannot be guaranteed that the system will operate exactly as intended without further testing on the actual robot.

8.5.3 Suggestions for improvement

Future work should focus on completing full deployment and validation of the system on the physical TIAGo robot, in order to confirm that the performance observed in simulation translates reliably to the real life.

Again, additional experiments with human participants in semi-controlled environments would also help to evaluate the system's robustness in natural interactions.

8.6 Objective 6 discussion

Objective 6:

Ensure compatibility with various robotic platforms.

8.6.1 Results

The system was designed and implemented using ROS (Robot Operating System) and a modular architecture. Thanks to this, the different components of the project could be integrated in a decoupled manner, facilitating reusability. Moreover, since ROS is widely adopted and compatible with a broad range of robotic platforms and hardware configurations, the system can be readily adapted and deployed across a heterogeneous set of robotic platforms. As a result, this objective can be considered successfully accomplished.

8.6.2 Limitations

The compatibility of the system has so far only been validated on ROS Noetic and tested with TIAGo. However, differences across ROS distributions or robot-specific implementations may require additional adaptation for seamless integration. Consequently, while the modular design facilitates portability, direct deployment on other platforms or with different ROS versions cannot be guaranteed without further adjustments.

8.6.3 Suggestions for improvement

Future work should focus on deploying the developed system on a variety of robotic platforms beyond TIAGo, in order to assess its generalization capabilities and the adaptations required.

Chapter 9

Conclusions

The objectives defined in Section 1 have guided the development, validation and assessment of the proposed Predictive Collision Avoidance (PCA) system. Overall, the project successfully met its aim of improving pedestrian collision avoidance in public mobile robots (PMRs) by integrating trajectory forecasting into the navigation stack of the TIAGo robot. The results confirm that the system enhances navigation performance, consistently providing the robot with a larger temporal margin to react before a potential collision occurs, thereby improving both safety and smoothness compared to the baseline configuration.

From a technical perspective, the project demonstrates that pedestrian trajectory prediction can be effectively integrated into a navigation framework with relatively low computational cost. Although strict real-time operation was not fully achieved due to constraints in the sampling rate of the pedestrian trajectory dataset, inference times remained consistently below 0.1 seconds, ensuring that navigation fluidity was not compromised. The modular and ROS-based design of the framework guarantees reusability and adaptability, enabling potential deployment beyond a single robotic platform. Furthermore, the simulation-based evaluation pipeline developed in this project constitutes a methodological benchmark that can be reused in future work to systematically assess predictive collision avoidance approaches.

From a research perspective, the introduction of the ACAT (Available Collision Avoidance Time) metric represents a novel contribution for the quantitative evaluation of predictive collision avoidance systems. This metric enabled a statistically rigorous comparison between the baseline and the predictive approach, demonstrating the robustness and consistency of the improvements. The results show that the PCA system achieves statistically significant improvements in both single-agent and multi-agent scenarios, providing strong evidence of the benefits of embedding prediction within PMR navigation systems.

From a practical standpoint, the system was designed for deployment on the TIAGo robot developed by PAL Robotics. While complete deployment on the physical robot could not be carried out within the scope of this project, the developed code provides a solid foundation for future trials on real hardware.

In summary, this work contributes to the literature with a novel pedestrian collision detection system that leverages trajectory prediction, a methodological benchmark for systematic validation, and the new performance metric ACAT. Beyond its academic relevance, the project also demonstrates practical value by being engineered for deployment on the TIAGo robot, bringing PMRs closer to safe and trustworthy integration into urban environments. Taken together, these contributions represent a promising step toward safer, more efficient, and socially compliant autonomous navigation systems.

Chapter 10

Future Work

Several directions remain open for future research to strengthen, validate and extend the Predictive Collision Avoidance (PCA) system. Future work should focus on refining the current system, validating it beyond simulation, and advancing toward more intelligent decision-making in autonomous navigation.

First, the system should be refined and re-iterated by implementing the suggestions for improvement identified in Chapter 8. For instance, higher-frequency pedestrian trajectory datasets (e.g., ≥ 10 Hz) could enhance the temporal resolution of the predictions, while applying model pruning [142] or extending the current parallelization to a larger number of GPUs could substantially improve the training efficiency of the trajectory prediction model. These refinements illustrate how the system could be made more robust.

Second, a critical step forward is the deployment and validation of the Predictive Collision Avoidance system on the TIAGo robot. Beyond the simulation results presented in this thesis, real-world testing will be essential to confirm system performance under practical conditions and to uncover potential problems before public deployment.

Third, future research should move beyond collision detection toward decision-making in conflict situations. Once a collision is predicted, the robot must not only react, but also determine the most appropriate course of action. This requires first enriching its understanding of the environment through semantic perception and intent inference, enabling it to distinguish between different types of agents (e.g., pets, bicycles) and anticipate their likely behaviours. Building on this, decision-making should be guided by cost functions that evaluate not only factors such as the time required to reach the goal or the feasibility of the planned path, as the TEB planner does, but also that respect a set of legal, social and ethical rules. Defining such a rulebook is not solely the task of engineers; rather, it requires societal input to establish and prioritise these rules in a hierarchical manner, a crucial step toward building robots that can operate safely, ethically and socially acceptable within shared spaces. Overall, this line of research represents the transition from prediction alone to cognitive navigation, where robots are capable of reasoning about the technical, legal, social, and ethical dimensions of interaction in human-populated environments.

In conclusion, future work on the PCA framework should advance along three directions: refining the system based on the identified improvements, validating it on the TIAGo robot, and extending it to integrate decision-making capable of handling conflict situations. Following these directions will take the PCA system from a simulation-based concept to an intelligent system ready for real-world use in complex urban environments.

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Appendix A

Appendix

Dataset name	Scenes no.	Scene type							
		I	II	III	LF	CA	Grp	Oth	IV
biwi_eth	388	5	77	179	35	31	38	82	127
biwi_hotel	163	8	80	64	10	13	25	28	11
cff_06	53201	95	11438	39583	14305	24753	724	9962	2085
cff_07	52152	77	11412	38549	14409	24043	716	9515	2114
cff_08	50985	71	10919	37935	13553	23571	700	9619	2060
cff_09	22336	46	5661	14487	4244	7752	439	4814	2142
cff_10	18309	27	4803	11739	3359	6201	398	3925	1740
cff_12	51278	67	11206	37891	14108	23505	671	9524	2114
cff_13	48871	88	10524	36165	12655	22556	690	9128	2094
cff_14	50662	73	10854	37479	14005	23056	688	9501	2256
cff_15	49514	76	10194	37035	13285	22752	742	9444	2209
cff_16	20735	45	5313	13209	3723	6667	440	4603	2168
cff_17	20163	30	5631	12769	3721	7229	476	3951	1733
cff_18	46643	57	10193	34121	12524	20329	652	9056	2272
crowds_students001	3381	67	332	2854	401	1223	1089	816	128
crowds_students003	3108	28	247	2631	438	1116	1169	769	202
crowds_zara01	553	1	87	331	49	95	141	80	134
crowds_zara02	908	39	191	517	119	184	257	129	161

Table A.1 continued from previous page

Dataset name	Scenes no.	Scene type							
		I	II	III	LF	CA	Grp	Oth	IV
crowds_zara03	546	7	99	332	72	105	142	98	108
lcas	1472	362	120	698	53	158	11	484	292
uni_examples	147	2	18	63	2	10	17	36	64
wildtrack	691	64	22	461	39	32	110	291	144

TABLE A.1: TrajNet++: Statistics of the training split.

Dataset name	Scenes no.	Dataset type							
		I	II	III	LF	CA	Grp	Oth	IV
biwi_eth	265	1	43	121	34	25	7	61	100
biwi_hotel	19	1	0	18	2	9	0	7	0
cff_06	23374	43	4765	17859	6533	11871	336	4005	707
cff_07	25354	43	4751	19915	7694	13078	339	4396	645
cff_08	21645	46	4150	16786	6199	10402	307	4190	663
cff_09	10730	26	2491	7431	2353	4034	151	2375	782
cff_10	9384	27	2463	6205	2006	3620	174	1840	689
cff_12	21014	28	4356	15975	6031	10356	272	3760	655
cff_13	20492	34	3483	16265	5831	9580	283	4277	710
cff_14	21110	31	3995	16404	6066	10206	340	4036	680
cff_15	20421	45	3736	15931	5778	9680	284	4096	709
cff_16	10186	28	2549	6860	2137	3826	174	2129	749
cff_17	8690	24	2287	5645	1728	3217	156	1737	734
cff_18	23566	34	5037	17827	6812	11768	349	4019	668
crowds_students001	1004	16	122	815	147	391	363	172	51

Table A.2 continued from previous page

Dataset name	Scenes no.	Dataset type							
		I	II	III	LF	CA	Grp	Oth	IV
crowds_students003	588	6	39	498	68	224	144	171	45
crowds_zara01	219	0	53	112	31	33	46	26	54
crowds_zara02	472	19	167	195	39	94	81	51	91
crowds_zara03	114	0	28	69	3	28	22	23	17
lcas	238	67	23	62	0	12	0	50	86
uni_examples	69	0	13	28	5	0	15	11	28
wildtrack	189	36	13	98	4	1	27	68	42

TABLE A.2: TrajNet++: Statistics of the validation split.

Dataset name	Scenes no.	Scene type							
		I	II	III	LF	CA	Grp	Oth	IV
biwi_eth	426	1	89	305	102	90	116	95	31
biwi_hotel	53	12	7	28	11	7	17	4	6
cff_06	13425	15	3636	9129	3476	5675	194	2247	645
cff_07	14177	18	3449	10069	3745	6166	167	2578	641
cff_08	12657	26	3416	8569	2934	5048	159	2395	646
cff_09	6158	16	1919	3615	939	1819	163	1263	608
cff_10	5849	16	1863	3442	961	1862	123	1149	528
cff_12	17369	27	4080	12632	4885	8027	245	2997	630
cff_13	12705	23	3186	8797	3037	5275	159	2370	699
cff_14	13833	22	3301	9838	3521	6045	162	2534	672
cff_15	13328	29	3370	9290	3170	5658	168	2490	639
cff_16	5267	13	1602	3008	799	1349	131	1165	644

Table A.3 continued from previous page

Dataset name	Scenes no.	Scene type							
		I	II	III	LF	CA	Grp	Oth	IV
cff_17	5850	10	1869	3384	891	1883	126	1112	587
cff_18	11148	16	3172	7288	2436	4213	120	2094	672
crowds_students001	745	17	83	596	98	188	191	238	49
crowds_students003	348	1	15	293	19	102	94	116	39
crowds_zara01	144	2	24	48	0	7	17	24	70
crowds_zara02	408	26	122	217	22	59	89	72	43
crowds_zara03	266	9	21	205	17	91	64	66	31
lcas	229	36	14	87	5	32	0	50	92
uni_examples	29	0	18	9	0	0	7	2	2
wildtrack	173	22	4	90	0	39	3	51	57

TABLE A.3: TrajNet++: Statistics of the testing split.

FIGURE A.1: Distribution by mean speed v_r in each dataset file. The histogram reports the number of scenes per 0.1 m/s interval of v_r .

FIGURE A.1: Distribution by mean speed v_r in each dataset file. The histogram reports the number of scenes per 0.1 m/s interval of v_r (continued).

FIGURE A.2: Distribution by motion direction–speed in each dataset file. The polar diagram shows the density of scenes by direction and speed, with the orange line indicating the median pedestrian speed v_r at each angle.

FIGURE A.2: Distribution by motion direction–speed in each dataset file. The polar diagram shows the density of scenes by direction and speed, with the orange line indicating the median pedestrian speed v_r at each angle (continued).